

EXAMINING CONTRACTS-BASED MORAL RIGHTS THROUGH ACADEMIC AND TRADE PUBLISHING

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INTRODUCTION

The author of a creative work receives a copyright that protects their economic interests in the work. With America's dominant utilitarian theory of intellectual property, this is to incentivize the work's creation.¹ Yet authors elsewhere and visual artists in the United States² often also receive a set of moral rights, non-economic rights that attempt to protect the author's personhood interests. While such rights are often justified by labor-desert or personality theories of intellectual property,³ there is increasing utilitarian scholarship that recognizes the value of moral rights for authors.⁴ In particular, there has been focus on the two moral rights under the Berne convention, (1) the right of attribution, receiving credit for one's work while not being credited for work that is not one's own, and (2) the right of integrity, preventing "distortion, mutilation or other modification of, . . ." one's work that "would be prejudicial to [the author's] honor or reputation."⁵ In fact, a recent Copyright Office study has examined the "patchwork" of specific and non-

¹ E.g. Stewart E. Sterk, *Rhetoric and Reality in Copyright Law*, 94 Mich. L. Rev. 1197, 1197 (1996), Mark A. Lemley, *Faith-Based Intellectual Property*, 62 UCLA L. Rev. 1328, 1330 (2015).

² The Visual Artists Rights Act. Codified in 17 U.S.C. § 106A amongst other sections.

³ Jeanne C. Fromer, *Expressive Incentives in Intellectual Property*, 98 Va. L. Rev. 1745, 1753 (2012), William Fisher, *Theories of Intellectual Property*, in NEW ESSAYS IN THE LEGAL AND POLITICAL THEORY OF PROPERTY (S. Munzer ed., Cambridge Univ. Press 2001). Utilitarianism, while dominant in American scholarship, is not the sole objective of US copyright law (which is instead more eclectic in nature).

⁴ E.g. Henry Hansmann & Marina Santilli, *Authors' and Artists' Moral Rights: A Comparative Legal and Economic Analysis*, 26 J. Legal Stud. 95, 98 (1997), Thomas F. Cotter, *Pragmatism, Economics, and the Droit Moral*, 76 N.C. L. Rev. 1, 1 (1997), Catherine L. Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due: The Law and Norms of Attribution*, 95 Geo. L.J. 49, 50 (2006), Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1747, Christopher Jon Sprigman et. al., *What's A Name Worth?: Experimental Tests of the Value of Attribution in Intellectual Property*, 93 B.U. L. Rev. 1389, 1390 (2013), Stefan Bechtold & Christoph Engel, *The Valuation of Moral Rights: A Field Experiment* 4 (Max Planck Institute for Research on Collective Goods, Preprint, 2017).

⁵ Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, art. 6bis(1), Sept. 9, 1886, 123 L.N.T.S. 233, revised at Paris July 24, 1971, 25 U.S.T. 1341, 1161 U.N.T.S. 3

specific federal and state laws that either directly or incidentally govern moral rights in the United States.⁶

This article addresses a subset of the moral rights-governing patchwork, contracts and copyright, specifically the utilitarian implications of effectuating attribution and integrity rights through the two (henceforth referred to as a “contracts-based moral rights”). To discuss the advantages and disadvantages of contracts-based moral rights as it functions in specific contexts, this article will provide an analytical framework then examine it through examples in the academic and trade book publishing industries.

This article ultimately attempts to achieve two objectives: (1) to identify the limitations of contracts-based moral rights, which primarily affect unsophisticated as well as poorly resourced authors for publishing, and (2) to identify the differing ways in which such limitations impact various subsets of authors.

Specifically, this article argues that the limitations of contracts-based moral rights — generated through a combination of legal doctrine, industry structure, and norms — are likely to affect the creative incentives of only a subset of authors: those who are sophisticated but poorly resourced. In this article’s publishing examples, the subset includes some more experienced trade book authors and potentially junior faculty. After all, heuristics and biases suggest that the unsophisticated author is less cognizant of the system’s limitations, *ex-ante*, while sophisticated well-resourced authors (potentially including senior faculty) can better effectuate moral rights, *ex-post*.

Setting aside this intermediate group of authors, a second source of inefficiencies instead lies in a contract-based system’s greater capacity to generate *ex-post* psychic harms from needless moral rights violations. Here, the article identifies both waivable and mandatory statutory regimes as offering the potential to raise authors’ creative incentives as well as reduce *ex-post* harms. Even a waivable regime can generate efficiency improvements in the non-contractual space against doctrinal limitations, and both likely offer superior results as compared to tweaking rules to improve their incidental protection capabilities.

Part I provides a background on moral rights, including moral rights laws as well as the utilitarian justifications for moral rights. In addition to the signaling and reputational benefits associated with moral rights, authors further receive intrinsic

⁶ [U.S. COPYRIGHT OFFICE, AUTHORS, ATTRIBUTION, AND INTEGRITY: EXAMINING MORAL RIGHTS IN THE UNITED STATES \(2019\)](#)

value from the rights. Their psychic gains and losses are socially relevant under a utilitarian framework. This article thus focuses on both the traditional issue of incentives to create as well as the question of efficient moral rights effectuation for its own intrinsic value.

Part II describes this paper's analytical framework on contracts-based moral rights, including the complications brought on by insights from behavioral economics, norms, and industry structure. At first instance, the effectiveness of a contracts-based moral rights system is determined by the ability of contractual coverage and copyright infringement to substitute the protection provided by a moral rights statute. Here, both norms and industry structure impact the actual degree of protection offered by the substitutes. Yet the unsophisticated authors' heuristics and biases suggest that ineffective moral rights protection will have only a limited impact on incentives to create, its harm instead residing with ex-post psychic externalities.

Part III sets up the more detailed exploration by providing a background of the actors in the academic and trade publishing industries. Here, the differing industry structures and differing incentives (directly financial with trade authors, less so with academics) allow for a discussion of a contracts-based moral rights system's effectiveness under different circumstances.

Part IV moves on to the contractual aspect of the system, discussing both the actual level of protection offered by contracts as well as their theoretical limits, in addition to the (potentially quite broad) breadth of coverage. More sophisticated and well-resourced players (well-known authors, senior academics) will achieve superior results through both the law as well as norms, while unsophisticated authors are more likely to be harmed, ex-post.

Part V discusses the non-contractual re-use space, primarily copyright's ability to effectuate moral rights against third parties but also the effectiveness of norms such as plagiarism. Benefits again accrue to more sophisticated and well-resourced players. Yet there are significant differences in the effectiveness of copyright infringement as a method of moral rights protection between the two industries: the thin slice of fair use egregious parodies for trade publishing versus the gaping holes of idea-expression distinction and agency costs for academics. Here, academic anti-plagiarism norms make up for much of copyright's doctrinal limitations.

Part VI summarizes the effectiveness of contracts-based moral rights in the two publishing industries, before describing the advantages and disadvantages of either

a waivable or mandatory statutory regime, as well as the alternative of legal adjustments. Finally, the paper briefly concludes.

I. BACKGROUND ON MORAL RIGHTS

A. Overview on Moral Rights Laws

Statutory protections for moral rights began in 19th century Europe,⁷ with the adopting civil law countries typically conceiving of them as an author's non-economic rights separate from copyright.⁸ Often justified under personality theory due to the notion of the "creative work as a Hegelian extension of the author's personality,"⁹ moral rights grant the author control of the work beyond copyright and include the rights of attribution and integrity, as well as in some jurisdictions: the right of withdrawal, the right of divulgation, the right to pseudonymity, the right to prevent destruction of the work, etc.¹⁰ From the various options listed above, the Berne convention adopted in 1928 the rights of attribution and integrity in Article 6bis:

(1) Independently of the author's economic rights, and even after the transfer of the said rights, the author shall have the right to claim authorship of the work and to object to any distortion, mutilation or other modification of, or other derogatory action in relation to, the said work, which would be prejudicial to his honor or reputation.¹¹

Most Berne signatory countries have adopted statutes protecting such moral rights – despite the Berne Convention's toothlessness – though the adopted rights show significant differences in scope, alienability and waivability.¹² For example, France's (considered the originator of modern moral rights) protections are

⁷ U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 10-11

⁸ *Id.*

⁹ Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1753

¹⁰ U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 13-14.

¹¹ Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, art. 6bis(1), Sept. 9, 1886, 123 L.N.T.S. 233, revised at Paris July 24, 1971, 25 U.S.T. 1341, 1161 U.N.T.S. 3

¹² U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 11-12, 15.

powerful, being perpetual, inalienable, and mandatory,¹³ while common law jurisdictions such as Canada and the UK tend to allow for waivers of the rights.¹⁴

The United States however disfavored such rights, perhaps due to its strong utilitarian traditions, and pushed for its exclusion from the more powerful Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Agreement (“TRIPS”).¹⁵ Instead, explicit federal statutory moral rights protection in the United States is limited to the Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990 (“VARA”), which grants the right of attribution, integrity, and the right to prevent destruction of works of “recognized stature” to artists of “works of visual art.”¹⁶ The rights provided are non-transferable waivable default rules further subject to copyright’s other limitations, including fair use.¹⁷ Moral rights, primarily attribution, were also previously protected by the Lanham Act until 2003, when the Supreme Court held in *Dastar Corp. v. Twentieth Century Fox Film Corp.*, that “there is no Lanham Act obligation to credit the original creator or copyright owner as the origin of the work.”¹⁸ The ruling mostly foreclosed the approach.

Instead, the United States currently protects moral rights through a patchwork of other laws, from 17 U.S.C. § 1202’s CMI protections, derivative works protection, to state law such as defamation, and contracts, even state moral rights laws.¹⁹ The Copyright Office ultimately concluded that the “current moral rights patchwork—including copyright law’s derivative work right, state moral rights statutes, and contract law—are generally working well.”²⁰ This article however explicitly emphasizes the limitations of protection through non-moral rights laws

¹³ Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1756.

¹⁴ See Hansmann & Santilli, *Authors' and Artists' Moral Rights*, *supra* note 4 at 124.

¹⁵ Elizabeth Schéré, *Where Is the Morality? Moral Rights in International Intellectual Property and Trade Law*, 41 *Fordham Intl. L.J.* 773, 774 (2018).

¹⁶ See 17 U.S.C. § 106A.

¹⁷ *Id.*

¹⁸ Justin Hughes, *American Moral Rights and Fixing the Dastar "Gap"*, 2007 *Utah L. Rev.* 659, 661 (2007).

¹⁹ The U.S.’s potential to effectuate moral rights through a patchwork of existing laws is widely recognized. And the U.S. Copyright Office has surveyed and discussed the applicability of various such laws. U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 1-3.

²⁰ *Id.* at 4.

or norms relative to a statutory system through a comparative discussion of academic and trade book publishing.²¹

B. Utilitarian Justifications for Moral Rights

Moral rights have generally been discussed under a personality theory framework, rather than the creative incentives-oriented welfare theory approach.²² Yet utilitarianism-oriented scholars have recognized the expressive creative incentives that may be generated by moral rights, the trademark or signaling aspect of moral rights to others (primarily for attribution), and relatedly, reputational externalities associated with moral rights. This recognition of the potential utilitarian benefits of moral rights does not imply agreement on the need for default rules, due to the availability of alternatives such as contracting along with behavioral concerns including the endowment effect.²³

At the first instance, the rights of attribution and integrity have value under a utilitarian framework because people ascribe value to being attributed / having their work protected,²⁴ while suffering pecuniary and non-pecuniary harms where a work is misattributed or mutilated. The ability for this value to serve as an incentive for creation is particularly emphasized by Fromer, who sees statutory moral rights as

²¹ Thus the article does not directly address federal and state moral rights statutes such as VARA. Additionally in the non-contractual space, the article will primarily focus on federal law, specifically copyright.

²² In fact, scholars at times have thought of personality and utilitarian theories as conflicting. Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1761 (citing in note 90 scholars such as Julie E. Cohen, Jane C. Ginsburg, Jessica Silbey, etc).

²³ Compare Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1790 (arguing for an attribution default rule in some circumstances) with Sprigman et al., *What is a name worth?*, *supra* note 4 at 1428 (arguing that the current U.S. system of no default attribution “probably results in more efficient . . . bargaining”).

²⁴ See e.g., Sprigman et al., *What is a name worth?*, *supra* note 4 at 1401 (describing the “intrinsic value” of attribution with concerns such as “psychic effect on . . . wellbeing”, as well as its “moral value”), Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 50 (mentioning that credit is “intrinsically valuable simply for the pleasure of being acknowledged.”), Alfred C. Yen, *When Authors Won't Sell: Parody, Fair Use, and Efficiency in Copyright Law*, 62 U. Colo. L. Rev. 79, 102-03 (1991) (using an efficiency analysis’ need to include the author’s emotional harms from a parody to critique the use of efficiency analysis for copyright), Thomas F. Cotter, *Pragmatism*, *supra* note 4 at 1 (Examples used in paper for right of integrity analysis in VARA context describe sense of harm). The experience of this emotional harm may be socially or culturally dependent, given different cultures’ differing perceptions on attribution, innovation, etc. Thus the relevance of intrinsic value under a utilitarian analysis may differ depending on the groups the law applies to. This paper does not address this issue but rather assumes the psychic harms as given.

an opportunity to generate incentives at low cost.²⁵ The value of attribution is reflected by empirical work,²⁶ the primacy of attribution in creative commons licenses,²⁷ and even anecdotes of psychic harms described in the ghost writing industry²⁸ as well as academia.²⁹ So too do we see the harms inflicted by altering work, from Hemingway's complaints upon editorial changes to the language of his work,³⁰ to notable case law such as the *Gilliam v. ABC* (the Monty Python case).³¹

²⁵ Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1747. The piece further briefly mentions damages for "personhood harms" as a part of remedies. *Id.* at 1792. Hansmann & Santilli, *Authors' and Artists' Moral Rights*, *supra* note 4 at 102, also contemplates non-pecuniary psychic losses suffered by the artist if a moral right is violated. However Hansmann & Santilli do not emphasize it in their work. *Id.* at 104 ("much of the incentive for adopting moral rights legislation derives from other considerations . . .").

²⁶ See Sprigman et al., *What is a name worth?*, *supra* note 4 at 1389 (testing the value placed upon attribution), and Bechtold & Engel, *The Valuation of Moral Rights*, *supra* note 4 at 1 (testing the value placed upon moral rights).

²⁷ 97%-98% of Creative Commons licenses users selected attribution such that it subsequently became a mandatory CC license. Glenn, Announcing (and explaining) our new 2.0 licenses, Creative Commons, May 25, 2004, <https://creativecommons.org/2004/05/25/announcingandexplainingournew20licenses/>.

²⁸ See e.g. Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 96 ("A recent memoir by a [successful] ghost writer . . . suggests that the ghost writing experience had some degrading qualities both for [the ghost writer] and for the person for whom she wrote."), Demian Farnworth, The Brutally Honest Truth About Ghostwriting, Raven, June, 2013, <https://raventools.com/blog/truth-about-ghostwriting/> ("I missed the attention, the recognition, the authority In fact, after about three months I was utterly depressed. Like, near suicidal."), Naomi D. Nakashima, The Psychological Toll of Being a Freelance Ghostwriter, Medium, July 31, 2021, <https://medium.com/swlh/the-psychological-toll-of-being-a-freelance-ghostwriter-fff9f1b38fb9> (emphasizing, amongst other issues, the loneliness and the lack of credit), Phyllis Romero, Lessons From a Ghostwriter: Why I'll never sell my fiction work again, The Writing Cooperative, Mar 12, 2019 ("Selling my fiction work was like selling a piece of myself.").

²⁹ E.g. Kimberly D. Becker, *Graduate students' experiences of plagiarism by their professors*, 73(2) Higher Education Quarterly 251 (2018) (describing a [graduate student] feeling "despondent that he never received credit for his hard work.", and that "four out of the five participants expressed feeling like they endured abuse or trauma."). Though those feelings may be generated in part by the harassment and retaliation they had faced at the university. See *id.*

³⁰ Dalya Alberge, 'You've bollixed up my book': letter reveals Hemingway's fury at being censored, The Guardian, Mar 29, 2020, <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2020/mar/29/youve-bollixed-up-my-book-letter-reveals-hemingways-fury-at-being-censored>

³¹ *Gilliam v. Am. Broad. Companies, Inc.*, 538 F.2d 14, 18 (2d Cir. 1976) (Monty Python being "allegedly 'appalled' at the discontinuity and 'mutilation' that had resulted from the editing done by Time-Life for ABC."). See also, Dennis Hevesi, Writer Who Is Suing Over Editing Is Told to Edit, New York Times, October 4, 1992, <https://www.nytimes.com/1992/10/04/nyregion/writer-who-is-suing-over-editing-is-told-to-edit.html> (writer complaining that abridged letter published without permission violates the integrity of his letter.).

Yet beyond the utility of the author, moral rights — primarily attribution — further serve a trademark-esque purpose as a market signal. After all, one generally expects a given novel to sell better if it is sold under the name of a famous author. Fisk further emphasizes the importance of attribution in employment contexts, both for the author in finding subsequent work, as well as for the counterparty in employing the most effective person.³² This signaling point also relates to the issue of reputational externalities, where the value of certain goods such as art is dependent on the artist's other goods.³³ For those limited goods where the reputational externality is significant, such as art, the right of integrity can serve as an opportunity to protect this value.

This article will emphasize the former approach of authors' utility in attribution and integrity. This recognition suggests that the article is directly concerned with the negative externality of psychic harms in misattribution and work distortion beyond its impact on the more traditional issue of creative incentives. After all, to the extent that moral rights are subjectively valued by creators, effectuating them under certain circumstances may be an efficient outcome that society should attempt to achieve so as to maximize social welfare (though much of the analysis will also apply if moral rights were justified under the alternative explanations of signaling and reputation).³⁴ Of course, acceptance of the utility of these rights and the effectuation of moral rights as an efficient outcome leaves the question of whether default rules / mandatory rules are necessary, with scholars often mentioning the existence of contracts and norms as an alternative regime.³⁵ This article thus explicitly compares the functioning of moral rights through contract relative to a statutory moral rights system, with special emphasis on norms, as well as other laws such as fair use.

³² Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 50. See also, Catherine J. Cameron, Reinvigorating U.S. Copyright with Attribution: How Courts Can Help Define the Fair Use Exception to Copyright by Considering the Economic Aspects of Attribution, 2 Berkeley J. Ent. & Sports L. 130, 133 (2013) (similar arguments such as misattribution reducing the amount of money an artist can make off of their art.).

³³ Hansmann & Santilli, *Authors' and Artists' Moral Rights*, *supra* note 4 at 104 (“[T]hose works we label ‘art’ commonly involve important reputational externalities, thus giving both the artist and others an unusually strong interest in protecting the integrity of individual works.”).

³⁴ See *infra* note 241 for brief comments on some differing implications.

³⁵ E.g. Sprigman et al., *What is a name worth?*, *supra* note 4 at 1402 (“... attribution in the U.S. becomes a subject of contract law and the operation of social norms . . .”), U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 129 (“Contracts and licenses, which are governed by state law, have been at the forefront of protecting moral rights in the U.S.”).

II. AN ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK FOR CONTRACTS-BASED MORAL RIGHTS

A contracts-based moral rights system effectuates moral rights by replacing the deterrence generated by a moral rights statute with (1) deterrence from breach of contract in the contractual context, and (2) deterrence from copyright infringement (amongst other laws) in the non-contractual context.³⁶ Each prong is further affected by norms, as well as industry structure and standards that may either facilitate or impede moral right effectuation. This issue of efficient effectuation directly implicates social welfare ex-post with socially-relevant psychic gains (and market signal benefits) from proper attribution and integrity protection, at the cost of transactions costs from effectuating moral rights. The amount of net utility received by creators further has the potential to be relevant ex-ante, as the overall expected value (expressive and financial) perceived by creators impacts their incentives to create works.³⁷ Comparing a contractual moral rights system with a statutory system on the related fronts of efficient moral rights effectuation and incentives for creation thus serves as the starting point for discussing the relative merits of the two systems.

A. Impact of Heuristics and Biases

An initial point of complications arises with the question of knowledge possessed by authors, as further complicated by the insights from behavioral economics. On both the effectuation and incentives fronts, the issue of the creator's sophistication is crucial as existing utilitarian scholarship in favor of as well as against moral rights generally assume sophisticated creators who appreciate the

³⁶ The non-contractual branch is not always recognized in the literature. See Sprigman et al., *What is a name worth?*, *supra* note 4 at 1429 (discussing IP markets and bargaining gaps but not the non-contractual implications of the lack of a default rule), Cotter, *Pragmatism*, *supra* note 4 at 73-75 (discussing third party effects on enjoying the work as well as the difficulties of binding subsequent purchasers but not analyzing the issue of infringers who may also violate moral rights).

³⁷ An additional source of incentives from the statutory regime may include the fact that counter-parties will now have to pay for non-attribution / non-integrity, increasing the amount of gains that accrue to the author where decreases in the other payments to the author fail to completely adjust for this shift. The ex-ante incentives generated by the increased value to the author where the rule grants the author the right is emphasized by Fromer as a part of her arguments for an attribution rule as an expressive incentive. Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1791 note 275.

law.³⁸ Yet authors with limited processing capabilities, who lack the requisite knowledge, and are affected by biases, may deviate predictably on the fronts.

On efficient effectuation, authors who lack the knowledge, or who are afflicted by biases such as overoptimism may be disproportionately willing to accept non-mutually beneficial deals that do not efficiently effectuate moral rights, thereby incurring unnecessary ex-post psychic harms. At the first instance, individuals generally do not read contracts in a meaningful manner.³⁹ Furthermore, limited processing capabilities and the lack of legal knowledge suggests that they generally lack the wherewithal to understand the full implications of the contract even if they read it.⁴⁰ Yet even when they do understand the problematic nature of the clauses in the abstract, overoptimism suggests that the authors will give insufficient weight to the chance of such a clause actually being enforced in their situation.⁴¹ Even understanding the clause, then, unsophisticated authors may be easily reassured into accepting such unfavorable terms, thereby incurring psychic harm ex-post.

On the other hand, if an author generally expects that the law protects their attribution and integrity rights (or that the contract is acceptable despite its text),⁴²

³⁸ For example, much of Fromer's analysis of the benefits of expressive incentives appears to assume that creators will actually appreciate rules that reflect their beliefs or react adversely to rules that fail to reflect their beliefs. See e.g. Fromer, *Expressive Incentives*, *supra* note 3 at 1784. Similarly, Sprigman et al.'s empirical study frames default terms for artists who have already created photos and extrapolates it to a discussion on default rules when it is unclear how real life contracting actively frames the terms of the agreement. Sprigman et al., *What is a name worth?*, *supra* note 4 at 1419.

³⁹ See Yannis Bakos, Florencia Marotta-Wurgler, & David R. Trossen, *Does Anyone Read the Fine Print? Consumer Attention to Standard-Form Contracts*, 43 J. Legal Stud. 1, 4-5 (2014) (large scale empirical study on whether consumers read EULAs).

⁴⁰ For example, Victoria Strauss, *Editing Clauses in Publishing Contracts: How to Protect Yourself, Writer Beware*, February 12, 2015, <https://accrispin.blogspot.com/2015/02/editing-clauses-in-publishing-contracts.html>, suggests that "[m]any authors skip right over [the clause described *infra* note 81], because on a surface reading it appears to protect the work from major changes." Similarly, she mentions hearing "of at least one publisher that used a revision clause to unilaterally enforce unwanted edits--at the author's expense." Presumably an author that read and understood the implications of a revision clause would have found another publisher.

⁴¹ EYAL ZAMIR & DORON TEICHMAN, *BEHAVIORAL LAW AND ECONOMICS* 276 (2018) (describing how overoptimism leads to the underestimation of breach of contract probabilities such that promisors "agree to harsh and inefficient liquidated damages clauses.").

⁴² Cf. John M. Darley, Kevin M. Carlsmith & Paul H. Robinson, *The Ex Ante Function of Criminal Law*, 35 Law & Soc'y Rev. 165, 165 (2001) (finding that people extrapolate from their personal views on whether an action ought to be criminalized when guessing whether the action is criminalized). Relatedly, Cotter suggests in the context of visual art that a lack of contractual moral rights clauses may be due to an artist's lack of foresight on the possibility of harms to their work's

then any creation would already reflect the utility from moral rights, without considering the artist's need to pay for the right or transactions costs (both of which reduce their expected net financial gains). Such an artist may further fail to consider the potentially reduced scope of protections (breadth and strength) in a contractual moral rights system, relative to a statutory system — even if they would subjectively feel harmed ex-post due to the lack of coverage.⁴³ Differences between moral rights systems on the more traditional incentives to create front may thus only be relevant for sophisticated authors, including those who become sophisticated after directly experiencing a violation of their perceived rights, as well as those indirectly learning from other sources.

The core concern on the incentives front then becomes whether a sophisticated, though boundedly rational, actor would place significant weight on the differences in the rate of moral rights effectuation between a contractual and a statutory system. This is ultimately an empirical question, with both overoptimism as well as the “diminishing sensitivity to changes in probability” between the boundaries of certainty⁴⁴ pushing in the direction of underestimating the differences.⁴⁵ On the flip side, the availability heuristic pushes in the direction of overestimation in the aftermath of learning of a rights violation, with those whose perceived rights were directly violated being the most likely to be affected.⁴⁶ Thus while ex-post psychic

integrity. Cotter, *Pragmatism*, *supra* note 4 at 55. This lack of foresight would similarly suggest identical incentives to create for such unsophisticated artists.

⁴³ For example, a scholar may publish a book under the assumption that it would only be cited within the academic community, where norms of attribution and integrity are strong (see discussion of plagiarism *infra* section V.A). If the contents of the book is re-used and modified outside the community where norms are weaker, the author may incur psychic harm ex-post. This is distinct from the situation where an author is indifferent, ex-post, to the re-use. After all, the author of a scholarly article in science may find it less relevant that the work is used as a part of science fiction. Similarly, it is unclear the degree to which people in general care about the name on the copyright registration as opposed to the name being publicly promoted.

⁴⁴ ZAMIR & TEICHMAN, *BEHAVIORAL LAW AND ECONOMICS*, *supra* note 41 at 34 (discussing the certainty effect demonstrated by Tversky & Kahneman).

⁴⁵ To the extent that the two options are closer to each other than the extremes of certainty and impossibility.

⁴⁶ ZAMIR & TEICHMAN, *BEHAVIORAL LAW AND ECONOMICS*, *supra* note 41 at 34-35 (“Tversky and Kahneman argued that people often determine the likelihood of events and the frequency of occurrences according to the ease of recalling similar events or occurrences.”). Both personal experience in the violation as well as learning of the violation of another's has this effect, though the former is likely greater due to its vividness. See *id.* at 36 (“more vivid events are often more accessible”). The troubling personality changes of graduate student victims of plagiarism, see *infra* note 224, may partly reflect this availability heuristic.

harms are clear, the unsophisticated author's incentives to create may be less affected by the differences in systems.

B. Impact of Norms

Norms are a second source of complexity, both in facilitating and impeding moral right effectuation on the contractual / non-contractual prongs. After all, both attribution as well as integrity often occurs within systems of norms.⁴⁷ On the contractual space prong, norms both impact whether there is a contract in the first place as well as supplement the contractual text to facilitate the functioning of a given activity. In contractual relationships, any norms of attribution and integrity that exist may have the potential to provide on average stronger levels of protection than text alone, given the costs of litigation.⁴⁸ Yet the emphasis away from the text also has the potential to cause harm by reducing the minimum level of protection in a given relationship. After all, an author's reliance on norms allows for the existence of less protective contractual terms that are likely not mutually desirable.

The impact of norms is similar in the non-contract space prong, as the existence of norms in industries such as chefs have granted protections even where intellectual property laws otherwise fail to cover the creations.⁴⁹ To be sure, such protections are limited in both their power⁵⁰ and scope, only covering those who are in the industry or are otherwise subject to those norms. Yet even when norms are powerful, as with academic plagiarism (discussed *infra* Section V.A), enforcement may be idiosyncratic against infringers.

While such idiosyncrises in the enforcement of norms may merely be random, they may also instead reflect power dynamics that privilege sophisticated authors who also possess clout, rather than those weaker and less sophisticated players that the law may desire to protect the most. Ultimately, under the twin fronts of efficient effectuation and incentives to create, the impact of norms is likely industry specific. And though powerful players may generally receive better moral rights effectuation and thus stronger incentives to create than weaker players, the interactions between

⁴⁷ E.g. Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 51.

⁴⁸ Though norms may also explicitly violate the rights of attribution and integrity.

⁴⁹ Emmanuelle Fauchart & Eric von Hippel, *Norms-Based Intellectual Property Systems: The Case of French Chefs*, 19(2) *Organization Science* 187, 189-90 (2008). See also Dotan Oliar & Christopher Sprigman, *There's No Free Laugh (Anymore): The Emergence of Intellectual Property Norms and the Transformation of Stand-Up Comedy*, 94 *Va. L. Rev.* 1787 (2008).

⁵⁰ For chefs, gossip and reputational loss is the main sanction. Fauchart & Von Hippel, *French Chefs*, *supra* note 49 at 193.

norms and incentives may also be more complex (if the ability to infringe is a substitute to creating original works).

C. Industry structure and standards

Industry structure and standards are the final source of complexity for the analysis. Industry structure determines the relative economic resources and sophistication of the parties. This includes the broader distribution of power between authors — a distribution implicating the effectuation of moral rights through norms — as well as narrower issues recognized most directly in the legal literature as inequality of bargaining power.

Inequality of bargaining power in a relationship allows one side to place disproportionate contractual terms and is most directly acknowledged by the legal system in its assumptions surrounding unconscionability and contracts of adhesion.⁵¹ Court analysis of the economic sources of inequality of bargaining power have included factors such as relative wealth, size, and monopoly power, with courts being concerned with situations that lack meaningful choices or opportunities to negotiate.⁵²

The lack of opportunities for negotiation relates to the issues presented by the industry standard level of treatment to creators, and the difficulties in deviating from the terms. To the extent that industry standard treatment effectuates an inefficient level of moral rights, difficulties deviating away from the standard will impede moral rights protection in the contractual space of both contracts-based and waivable statutory regimes. And specific industry standards such as the use of work-for-hire doctrine or copyright assignments will further implicate moral rights protection in the non-contractual space. Such issues have the potential to limit the benefits of a contracts-based moral rights regime or a waiver regime to those authors with the sophistication and the resources to negotiate away from the standard.

The difference in contractual outcomes with powerful, well-resourced, and sophisticated creators is shown through the rates of artists' waivers of their VARA moral rights by contract. A 2003 survey of artists regarding VARA showcases the knowledge of experienced artists with more than 15 commissioned works a year, with such artists having 100% knowledge on the waivability of moral rights rather

⁵¹ Daniel D. Barnhizer, *Inequality of Bargaining Power*, 76 U. Colo. L. Rev. 139, 141 (2005).

⁵² *Id.* at 199-200.

than only 52% overall.⁵³ Furthermore, in both the 1995 and 2003 surveys, artists represented by agents and those whose art provides income in excess of \$25,000 both more frequently turned down offers because of waiver clauses as well as more frequently insisted on striking a waiver clause than the general respondents.⁵⁴

Yet resources and influence are a potential further requirement as industry structure may mean a trade-off between moral rights and finances. Take the example of final cuts in film, which invokes the right of integrity for directors. As the finances and multiple interests of American filmmaking have moved away from studios providing final cuts privileges to directors, obtaining this privilege for most directors now involves either accepting a tighter budget, reduced compensation, or both (if it's on the table at all).⁵⁵ Influential directors are an exception however, as their value within the industry means that they can still be expected to obtain the privilege.⁵⁶ Such trade-offs are likely industry dynamic dependent, and are likely less significant in the realm of VARA art purchases.

After sketching out the analytical framework as well as the sources of complexity, this paper applies the framework by comparing the examples of academic and trade publishing.

III. ACTORS IN THE PUBLISHING INDUSTRY

While both publishing written work, the academic and trade book publishing industries possess differing industry standards, differing business models, differently incentivized players, as well as differing levels of protection afforded

⁵³ RayMing Chang, note, *Revisiting the Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990: A Follow-Up Survey About Awareness and Waiver*, 13 Tex. Intell. Prop. L.J. 129, 159 (2005) (table 2-2: Aware that Moral Rights can be waived).

⁵⁴ Id. at 166-67 (Table 4-1-C: Have Turned Down Offer Because of Waiver Clause and Table 4-1-D: Have Insisted a Waiver Clause be Struck.).

⁵⁵ Tom Brook, Director v studio: Who should have final cut?, BBC, June 2, 2014, <https://www.bbc.com/culture/article/20140603-director-v-studio-whos-right>

⁵⁶ Id. Whether this arrangement is efficient is a separate question to the extent that the director ultimately produces a movie that would have been substantially better for audiences had the studio been able to edit it. Relatedly, while many films were colorized to great controversy in the 80s, the widely renowned film, *Citizen Kane*, was not, in part due to contractual provisions that “could [have been] read to prohibit colorization without permission of the [director’s] estate.” John Antczak, *We’ll Never Know If Rosebud Was Red*, AP News, February 14, 1989, <https://apnews.com/article/3da27b3969212eb7885db3dbd81b597e>. There was also public outcry at the time, which further reflects the benefits of being influential.

by copyright law.⁵⁷ This allows for a comparison to showcase both factors contributing to the effectiveness of moral rights effectuation as well as the role of the complexities described above. Given the disaggregated nature of copyright for differing subject matters however, the contractual system's performance in the publishing industry should not be considered an argument for or against moral rights by contract generally.

A. Academic Publishing

With products consisting of both books as well as journal articles, academic publishing generally consists of full-time scholars employed by universities publishing articles with specialized publishers for other scholars to read.

1. Academic Publishers

The academic publishing industry is generally highly concentrated, with a few large publishers such as Elsevier and Springer-Nature publishing the vast majority of journal articles and academic books,⁵⁸ a product of mergers and acquisitions within the field.⁵⁹ Combine this concentration with effective legal representation and the publishers are likely sophisticated while possessing strong bargaining power on the terms of publication.

Yet at least for journals, academic publishers have generally devolved the decision-making authority on what to publish and in what form to editorial boards of volunteer academics,⁶⁰ with such editors further having the power to retract

⁵⁷ This paper will not systematically discuss the varied other forms of publishing: including blogs, business publications, news articles etc. The types of and strengths of norms may differ under such circumstances as well as the resources and relative sophistication of the actors, which will impact the effectiveness of a contracts-based moral rights system. To the extent that work-for-hire doctrine applies in such relations, there may be significant agency problems, to be discussed in infra Section V.B.4.

⁵⁸ Vincent Larivière, Stefanie Haustein, & Philippe Mongeon, *The Oligopoly of Academic Publishers in the Digital Era*, 10(6) PLoS ONE (2015).

⁵⁹ George Chen, Alejandro Posada & Leslie Chan, *Vertical Integration in Academic Publishing: Implications for Knowledge Inequality*, in *CONNECTING THE KNOWLEDGE COMMONS — FROM PROJECTS TO SUSTAINABLE INFRASTRUCTURE* (L. Chan, P. Mounier eds. OpenEdition Press 2019).

⁶⁰ Susan D'Agostino, *Why you should join a journal's editorial board*, Nature, August 7, 2019, <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-02410-0#:~:text=These%20positions%20are%20usually%20unpaid,new%20contacts%20in%20your%20discipline>. But see, Michael Dougherty, *The peer reviewers and editor wanted to publish my paper. The legal team rejected it.*, Retraction Watch, June 2, 2021,

articles when necessary. The ability to initiate retractions means that editors play a significant role in the academic norms against plagiarism (discussed *infra*, Section V.A). Academic books on the other hand are published more conventionally with paid editors (and academic advisors).

Legal scholarship presents an exception, both in the trend of concentration and in the selection process, with most law journals being affiliated with law schools and edited by law students rather than scholars. While the legal knowledge associated with law schools brings about sophistication, and the prestige associated with certain publishing institutions brings some bargaining power, the dynamic of students editing the work of professors may ultimately suggest less bargaining power on contractual terms than in general academic publishing.

This distinction between legal and non-legal scholarship extends to the treatment of intellectual property, with non-legal academic publications generally involving an assignment of copyright to the journal publisher, in contrast to licensing agreements to the journal with legal scholarship. Open access publishing is an increasing exception in non-legal academia due to the frequent use of creative commons licenses there. Though even then, some agreements involve the publisher being first granted an exclusive license, and the publisher then applying the CC license instead.⁶¹

On to business models: while individuals may pay for access to individual journal articles, the package sale of multiple journal subscriptions to universities is the primary source of revenues for academic publishers. Supplementing this primary model in the face of the rise of open access publishing (with such articles freely accessible to all) is the article processing charge, charged to either the author, or more likely their research funder / institution in order to publish the work. Academic books are sold more conventionally, and may either be aimed at universities, e.g. research handbooks, or students with textbooks. Note the fact that authors are generally not paid royalties for the authorship of journal articles, though they are for academic books. Instead, the academic authors have particular interests when publishing.

<https://retractionwatch.com/2021/06/02/the-peer-reviewers-and-editor-wanted-to-publish-my-paper-the-legal-team-rejected-it/> (describing legal reviewers that publishers maintain).

⁶¹ License Agreement CC BY-NC-ND version, Elsevier, March 2022, https://www.elsevier.com/data/assets/pdf_file/0009/1243188/CC-BY-NC-ND-JPLA_updated_March-2022.pdf (“I hereby grant to Journal Owner an exclusive publishing and distribution license” and “The publisher will apply the Creative Commons Attribution-Noncommercial-NoDerivative Works 4.0 International License (CC-BY-NC-ND) to the Article”).

2. Academic Authors

Academic authors generally do not publish for money (but see textbooks). Instead, proper attribution for one's work is crucial. This emphasis on attribution is mostly effectuated through unwritten industry standards between authors and publishers as well as norms amongst authors in academia, though less so through contracts.

The emphasis on attribution comes as scholars' publishing relates heavily to their careers in the university system. Early career researchers publish to obtain roles at institutions, while professors publish to obtain tenure, finally publishing to obtain prestige or renown in the field. This requirement for research, the so-called "publish or perish,"⁶² increases their reliance on academic publishers despite the fact that academic authors are not directly financially dependent on the revenues of publication. On the other hand, most academic authors have at least the potential to be well advised by their university libraries, increasing their potential sophistication.⁶³ And legal scholars in particular are likely the most sophisticated.

At least in principle, academic publishing is the interaction between sophisticated, though differently resourced, parties.

B. Trade Book Publishing

Trade book publishing involves the publication of fiction and non-fiction books aimed at the general public and sold at bookstore chains such as Barnes & Noble, online retailers such as Amazon, as well as digitally through e-reader stores.

1. Trade Publishers

Trade book publishers are similarly concentrated in the US, with a "big five" of publishers such as Penguin Random House and HarperCollins having most of the market share,⁶⁴ again a product of mergers and acquisitions.⁶⁵ Other options include both smaller (potentially even predatory) publishers, particularly for early

⁶² See e.g. Seema Rawat & Sanjay Meena, *Publish or perish: Where are we heading?*, 19(2) J Res Med Sci 87 (2014).

⁶³ Cf. Office for Scholarly Communication, For Authors, Harvard Library, 2018, <https://osc.hul.harvard.edu/authors/>

⁶⁴ Thad McIlroy, What the Big 5's Financial Reports Reveal About the State of Traditional Book Publishing, *Book Business*, August 5, 2016, <https://www.bookbusinessmag.com/post/big-5-financial-reports-reveal-state-traditional-book-publishing/>

⁶⁵ John b. [Thompson](#), *Trade Publishing*, in THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF PUBLISHING 5 (A. Phillips & M. Bhaskar eds. 2019).

authors,⁶⁶ as well as the opportunity for self-publishing in physical printings as well as digitally through online platforms such as Amazon.⁶⁷ Almost all publishers are thus sophisticated actors, with the larger ones further having greater bargaining power. Unlike academic publishers however, the large trade book publishers no longer require an assignment of copyright from the author. Instead, exclusive licenses to publish are the industry standard.⁶⁸

The business model of trade publishing is more conventional with individual book sales being the primary source of revenue, and advances / royalty payments being paid out to authors. Thus the emphasis on marketing and publicity to increase awareness of new works, with the brand of the author being particularly important.⁶⁹ The most lucrative of such authors may either be brand-name authors with loyal fans and regular publishing patterns,⁷⁰ or celebrities / public figures with brand-awareness from other fields.⁷¹ In either case, there may be industry demand for ghost writers to capitalize on the brand-awareness in the face of time or skill constraints of the supposed author.⁷² The uneven distribution of revenues and royalties creates much diversity in the positions of trade authors.

2. Trade Authors

After all, trade authors may vary from self-represented early career authors with day jobs to professionally represented super star authors. A concern for the finances of publication is generally present, though its significance depends on the author. Payment structures are generally explicit in contracts. Attribution is also important,

⁶⁶ See e.g. Emily Harstone, *The Top 25 Publishers for New Authors*, *Authors Publish*, October 20, 2020, <https://authorspublish.com/the-top-25-publishers-for-new-authors/> (listing many independent companies, and warning that “no legitimate established presses specifically look for unpublished authors”).

⁶⁷ Thompson, *Trade Publishing*, *supra* note 65 at 12-13.

⁶⁸ Authors, *Keep Your Copyrights. You Earned Them.*, *Authors Guild*, August 13, 2015, <https://www.authorsguild.org/industry-advocacy/authors-keep-your-copyrights-you-earned-them/>

⁶⁹ Thompson, *Trade Publishing*, *supra* note 65 at 9.

⁷⁰ *Id.* at 7.

⁷¹ E.g. Jim Farber, *Celebrity autobiographies are bigger business than ever, though some legends are keeping mum*, *New York Daily News*, Apr 13, 2014, <https://www.nydailynews.com/entertainment/celebrity-memoirs-bigger-business-article-1.1751111> (a celebrity autobiography’s “success caused what book agent Sarah Lazin calls ‘a feeding frenzy. Publishers started looking for any star who has a clear fan base.’”).

⁷² E.g. Caroline Howe, *Meet the ghostwriters who secretly pen bestselling celebrity memoirs*, *New York Post*, January 22, 2022, <https://nypost.com/2022/01/22/meet-the-ghostwriters-who-pen-bestselling-celebrity-memoirs/>

though again varied due to the willingness of some to trade away attribution as in ghost writing. Yet while ghost writing tends to be explicit about non-attribution, attribution is otherwise generally not reflected in contracts, instead being a norm as with academic publishing.

On the front of diversity: On one end, the self-represented early career author is likely both unsophisticated and has low bargaining power. With no track record of sales, this author is more likely to deal with the smaller publishers from a position of disadvantage. This is mirrored by the self-represented inexperienced ghost writer who has a lesser understanding of the business and the implications of ghost writing. The intermediate position comes from (more likely) professionally represented authors with experience in the field, who have the sophistication, though not necessarily the bargaining power, when interacting with publishers. Finally, professionally represented super star authors have both the sophistication as well as the audience to obtain favorable deals as publishers compete over their lucrative works.

Yet while trade publishing showcases a diverse set of players on both the sophistication as well as the resources front, mitigating factors may raise the sophistication of inexperienced authors and raise the bargaining power for authors as a group. The Authors Guild provide legal advice and support to existing authors who pay their membership fees,⁷³ and groups such as the Authors Alliance provide general legal and industry information to authors.⁷⁴

IV. COVERAGE BY CONTRACT

To discuss the effectiveness of a moral rights system effectuated by contracts, one must first discuss the situation where there is coverage by contract. Here, both the level of protection as well as the breadth of coverage are relevant. The actual level of protection within the publishing industries is key. Yet the paper also discusses limitations to the level of protection that contracts may potentially grant, both with contract law's doctrinal limitations as well as possibly fair use.

⁷³ Join, Authors Guild, n.d., <https://www.authorsguild.org/industry-advocacy/authors-keep-your-copyrights-you-earned-them/> (legal help being provided to associate membership and up tiers).

⁷⁴ Issues for Authors, Authors Alliance, n.d., <https://www.authorsalliance.org/our-issues/> (examples sections include “Managing Authors’ Rights: We help authors understand and manage the rights necessary to make their works broadly available now and in the future.”).

A. Actual Level of protection with contractual coverage

The fact that contracts cover a given relationship suggests at least the potential to enforce moral rights where it is desirable to do so. The situation on actual levels of moral rights protection is complex, beginning with the (necessarily incomplete) text, against the backdrop of default rules and case law, while being further influenced by the norms surrounding the relationship.

1. The Contractual Text

The starting point of courts' interpretation of contracts, the text has the potential to be highly specific. This is the case in certain industries with sophisticated parties on both sides such as the film industry's detailed credit system.⁷⁵ And collective bargaining in France has brought a similar level of specificity in their standard publishing contract.⁷⁶ As the text is necessarily incomplete, however, norms and courts will play a role. The fact that neither scholarly article publishing contracts, further discussed in the context of norms in the next section, nor trade book publishing contracts generally mention attribution to the author reflects this incompleteness.

Yet even if the text is specific, it does not necessarily bring about the efficient outcome, as contract-related concerns are implicated by both inequality of bargaining power as well as heuristics and biases. While a well-known trade book author with agent representation is likely to have the bargaining power to obtain a custom contract, inequality of bargaining power may very well apply when an unknown author negotiates with a large corporation and is presented with a standard form contract. The fact that an Australian exploratory study of book publishing contracts found that 44% of their examined contracts took “term-long exclusive rights, worldwide, in all languages” has the potential to reflect this inequality of

⁷⁵ See e.g. Screen Credits Manual, Writers Guild of America, https://www.wga.org/uploadedfiles/credits/manuals/screenscredits_manual10.pdf. Yet even then, there are limits to who gets credited within the system, which becomes a matter of norms. Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 77-78 (describing writer complaints of insufficiently transparent rules, storyboard artists' complaining about writers being given credit for their creative work, etc).

⁷⁶ See Standard contract, Société des gens de lettres, September 29, 2017, https://www.sgdl.org/phocadownload/Juridique/Sample_Contract_-_28.11.20171.pdf (“derived from a Union Agreement signed between the French publishers' union (SNE) and the French authors' association (CPE)” and containing explicit provisions such as the publisher “shall further include the Author's name or nickname as indicated by the latter, on the first page of the Work”)

bargaining power.⁷⁷ And academic journal publishing as a whole similarly reflects this issue given the prevalence of standard contracts.

Such issues of economic differences are combined with differences in the knowledge and relative sophistication of the players,⁷⁸ and high search costs only exacerbates the issue.⁷⁹ This situation is reflected by the fact that there is an entire site for trade book writers, “Writer Beware,” that “shin[es] a bright light into the dark corners of the shadow-world of literary scams, schemes, and pitfalls.”⁸⁰ The site’s blog post on editing clauses, which implicates the right of integrity, showcases the problematic terms that are agreed upon by unsophisticated authors. While it is clear that sophisticated well-resourced authors would rarely agree to a publisher's right to unilaterally make content edits without consent, many publishers have clauses that do just that.⁸¹ And it is the unsophisticated authors who either do not comprehend the implications of the terms or are overoptimistic that ultimately sign without negotiating for amendments.

Limited processing capabilities alongside transaction costs in seeking advice also bring about a second concern for authors, their potential to fall into traps even when advice is available. So despite the fact that academics can generally obtain sophisticated advice from libraries, some may still become the victim of predatory journals (which have issues that vary from excessive charges alongside substandard

⁷⁷ Joshua Yuvaraj & Rebecca Giblin, *Are Contracts Enough? An Empirical Study of Author Rights in Australian Publishing Agreements*, 44 Melb. U. L. Rev. 380, 406 (2020). The U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 136, also describes the concerns of advocacy groups of widespread adoptions of waivers of moral rights due to “unequal negotiating positions”.

⁷⁸ Barnhizer, *Inequality of Bargaining Power*, *supra* note 51 at 200.

⁷⁹ See *Id.* at note 342 (citing DiMatteo for the concern that “high search costs may lead consumers to contract with [the] first firm they approach regardless of contract terms”).

⁸⁰ About Writer Beware, Writer Beware, n.d. <https://accrispin.blogspot.com/> (“sponsored by the Science Fiction and Fantasy Writers of America, with additional support from the Mystery Writers of America, the Horror Writers Association, and the American Society of Journalists and Authors.” and ranked one of “100 Best Websites for Writers 2021”).

⁸¹ Strauss, *Editing Clauses in Publishing Contracts*, *supra* note 40, describes clauses such as: “Publisher shall have the right to correct errors, and/or edit and revise the Work for any and all uses contemplated under this Agreement (collectively “Editing”), provided that the meaning of the Work is not materially altered.” The clause suggests that tone and style may change substantially.

services to outright fraud).⁸² Thus the availability of discussion papers and websites for academics on how to avoid predatory journals.⁸³

The potential difference in contractual outcomes with powerful, well-resourced, and sophisticated creators is demonstrated by examples in academic book publishing. There exists negotiated contracts with clauses that vary from greater retained intellectual property rights to ones that allow for Creative Commons release of the contents online.⁸⁴ The policies of powerful institutions may also bring about change as Harvard supports its open access article publication policy (established 2008, before open access was as widely adopted) through providing author addendums that amend journals' standard contracts.⁸⁵ Such authors and institutions are likely able to generate similarly superior outcomes on moral rights effectuation if necessary.

Ultimately, the actual level of protection by contractual text may vary substantially, perhaps being far lower than the potential level of protection that may reasonably be negotiated. Here, norms have the potential to both advance moral rights protections as well as impede them.

2. Role of (contract-space) Norms

Authorship credit and article editing in academic publishing showcases the mixed impact of norms, both their importance in enabling publication, as well as their status as a substitute to contractual clauses with the potential to reduce the legal minimum of protection.

Take the example of journal article and textbook publishing contracts, where attribution and integrity for the author is likely to be a prime consideration. Yet the contracts of American journals generally fail to mention attribution for the author,

⁸² Discussion Document: Predatory Publishing, Committee on Publication Ethics, 4 (November 2019). Others knowingly publish in predatory journals. See More than 5,000 German scientists have published papers in pseudo-scientific journals, NDR, July 7, 2018, https://www.ndr.de/der_ndr/presse/More-than-5000-German-scientists-have-published-papers-in-pseudo-scientific-journals,fakescience178.html (“[S]tudy authors have taken advantage of the services offered by such predatory publishers to quickly publish their research results without having to subject themselves to the peer review process.”).

⁸³ See e.g. Journals, Think. Check. Submit., n.d., <https://thinkchecksubmit.org/journals/>

⁸⁴ E.g. Private Correspondence with professors at Harvard Law School (mentioning specific clauses they have negotiated for their academic books).

⁸⁵ Office for Scholarly Communication, Open Access Policies, Harvard Library, 2018, <https://osc.hul.harvard.edu/policies/>, Office for Scholarly Communication, For Authors, Harvard Library, 2018, <https://osc.hul.harvard.edu/authors/> (providing link to author addendum generator).

instead emphasizing attribution to the journal of original publication.⁸⁶ In fact, the non-explicit nature of attribution is seen in model trade book publishing contracts internationally, having little detail even in countries with moral rights — with the notable exception of the French collectively bargained publishing contract (which describes the attribution obligations in detail).⁸⁷ While the effective functioning of publication showcases the power of norms and standards, the fact that norms and industry standards are emphasized instead of text also enables the existence of less protective contractual terms in academic journal publishing — a lower degree of legally enforceable minimum protection.

Editing, which has the potential to implicate the right of integrity, reflects the problems associated with this deemphasis as there exists a range of clauses on this front. On one hand, certain law review publishing contracts specify editing, responding to edits, as well as both parties giving approval for final publication.⁸⁸ Yet this is not the case for other academic fields and their publishers, which range from non-contemplation of editing (as with Elsevier’s journal contract), reserving the ability to request changes only for infringement and ethics violations (with Wiley), to generally reserving the ability “to make such editorial changes as may be necessary to make the Article suitable for publication” in the case of Routledge.⁸⁹ While the norms associated with publication are unlikely to be violated, legal protection with Routledge is lower where norms are violated. The fact that Routledge’s terms are not generally considered worse than other publishers reflect the ability of norms to facilitate the existence of less protective actual terms.

⁸⁶ See e.g. Wiley Sample Publishing Contract, Ohio State Law Journal contract (on file with author). This emphasis on journal attribution may potentially be explained by the author’s tendency to reuse their own work rather than strictly follow copyright law, while in the case of attributing to the author by the publisher, the industry expectation is that they do so.

⁸⁷ Compare France’s SGDL [standard contract](#) (“derived from a Union Agreement signed between the French publishers’ union (SNE) and the French authors’ association (CPE)” and containing explicit provisions such as the publisher “shall further include the Author’s name or nickname as indicated by the latter, on the first page of the Work”) with US’s Author’s Guild Model Book [contract](#) (not explicitly mentioning attribution though asking author to grant permission if name used in marketing), Finland’s non-fiction sample [contract](#) (which does not mention attribution) and Germany’s standard publishing [contract](#) (a vague “The publisher is obliged to appropriately identify the author as the author of the work.” (machine translated)).

⁸⁸ See e.g. Yale Journal of International Law contract, Seton Hall Law Review (on file with author).

⁸⁹ Compare Taylor Francis Sample Publishing Agreement with Wiley Sample Publishing Agreement and Elsevier Sample Publishing Agreement (on file with author and available on websites). All three are major academic journal publishers.

A similar issue presents itself with the de-emphasis of attribution in the text of the contracts, as shown in the case of *Zyla v. Wadsworth, Division of Thomson Corp.*⁹⁰ Zyla, the co-author of a college textbook who was working on its 4th edition alongside the book's lead author, decided to withdraw from the fourth edition after the publisher repeatedly delayed the submission deadline in favor of the lead author.⁹¹ Zyla had informed the publisher both that she would not participate further and that her already submitted revisions should not be used in the work.⁹² She then agreed to sign a letter indicating her non-participation and her acceptance of reduced royalties under her initial publishing agreement.⁹³ In actuality, Zyla's revisions were used in the lead author's solely-authored fourth edition and she thus initiated the lawsuit.⁹⁴

Zyla lost on multiple fronts. She had no copyright infringement claim as copyright in the revisions were assigned to the publisher as a part of her initial agreement, the Lanham act claims were foreclosed by *Dastar*, and there was no breach of contract (as there was no contract between Zyla and the lead author).⁹⁵ Yet the fact that Zyla withdrew and ultimately lost came from her expectation that her revisions would not be used without permission. This was an expectation that existed despite a contract which granted her limited rights on paper. Here, the potential for norms to reduce protections is shown as Zyla may have decided not to withdraw otherwise. And unlike trade book publishing where problematic editing terms are criticized (though less so the lack of attribution),⁹⁶ the lack of attribution and editing clauses are considered the norm in academia.

The *Zyla* case also showcases the issue of industry standards, as she had the potential to succeed on the copyright claim if not for the dominant academic industry practice of copyright assignment. While Zyla likely did not attempt to negotiate out of copyright assignment due to industry norms, it would have been difficult for even a sophisticated author to negotiate the shift so as to better effectuate moral rights. The assignment of copyright limits the author's ability to

⁹⁰ *Zyla v. Wadsworth, Div. of Thomson Corp.*, 360 F.3d 243 (1st Cir. 2004). Another case with similar attribution issues include *Cleary v. News Corp.*, 30 F.3d 1255, 1258 (9th Cir. 1994) (lawsuit under the Lanham Act for attribution in Robert's rules of order).

⁹¹ *Zyla*, 360 F.3d at 246.

⁹² *Id.* at 248.

⁹³ *Id.*

⁹⁴ *Id.* at 248-49.

⁹⁵ *Id.* at 246.

⁹⁶ See Strauss, *Editing Clauses in Publishing Contracts*, *supra* note 40.

effectuate moral rights both within and outside the contractual relationship (see *infra* Section V.B.4 for discussion of copyright infringement and agency problems), and the difficulties in moving away from this model may prevent even a sophisticated author from better effectuating moral rights.

Finally, the lack of a contract between Zyla and the lead author reflects the fact that academic norms may also impede mutually beneficial ex-ante contracting between potential co-authors (see *infra* Section V.A for a discussion of plagiarism in particular). There is much discussion of the issues associated with co-authorship practices,⁹⁷ including power dynamics between professor and student that determines whose names are credited as authors in collaborations,⁹⁸ as well as conflicts where co-authors disagree in the content of the work.⁹⁹ Yet co-authorship agreements that may solve such problems ex-ante are comparatively rare, and authors may feel suspicious of such agreements.¹⁰⁰ Relying on the default rules of copyright law, however, can generate problematic results when attempting to enforce moral rights in the potential co-authors context (see *infra* Section V.B.1 for a discussion of the joint work rules that generate such results). As a general matter,

⁹⁷ E.g. Jeffrey I. Seeman & Mark C. House, *Authorship Issues and Conflict in the U.S. Academic Chemical Community*, 22(6) *Accountability in Research* 346 (2015), Howard J. Curzer, *Authorship and justice: Credit and responsibility*, 28(1) *Accountability in Research* 1 (2021), Nicole A. Vasilevsky et al., *Is authorship sufficient for today's collaborative research? A call for contributor roles*, 28(1) *Accountability in Research* 23 (2021).

⁹⁸ Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 102 (describing difficulties of graduate students in challenging claims of credit by senior professors). See also, Becker, *Graduate students' experiences*, *supra* note 29 at 257.

⁹⁹ Though perhaps in less formal contexts. E.g. Natalie Parletta, A three-step process for resolving paper disputes, *nature index*, December 8, 2020, <https://www.natureindex.com/news-blog/a-three-step-process-for-resolving-paper-authorship-disputes> (citing a researcher consultant's claim that "There's a widespread discussion of this phenomenon of being coerced into putting your name on something or overemphasizing results that you're not totally happy with."), Richard B. Primack, John A. Cigliano, & Chris Parsons, Co-authors gone bad – how to avoid publishing conflicts, Elsevier, July 9, 2014, <https://www.elsevier.com/connect/co-authors-gone-bad-how-to-avoid-publishing-conflicts> (providing a hypothetical example where "[a] co-author blocks the publication of a paper because he/she does not agree with their co-authors' revisions."), Author disagreement regarding article corrections (Case), Committee on Publication Ethics, 2015, <https://publicationethics.org/case/author-disagreement-regarding-article-corrections>.

¹⁰⁰ E.g. Primack et al., *Co-authors gone bad*, *supra* note 99 (The step of an agreement "is perhaps taken too rarely, whether because scientists do not like rigid agreements, feel that developing agreements wastes time that would better be spent doing research, or that developing such an agreement could offend some of the co-authors."). Why You Need a 'Science Prenup' for Successful Collaboration, *Brown University Advance*, <https://web.archive.org/web/20190129115303/https://www.brown.edu/initiatives/translational-research/news/2018/04/why-you-need-science-prenup-successful-collaboration>

the existence of norms ex-ante may thus lead to a greater reliance on incidental protections, including copyright, ex-post.

Ultimately, norms and industry standards have the potential to both strengthen and reduce actual contractual protection. They are necessary for the effective functioning of the publishing system given insufficient contractual text. Yet they impede the greater protections that explicit contractual terms will bring.

B. Limits to the level of potential level of protection

The incomplete text and the role of norms showcase the ways in which actual contractual protection falls short of its potential. At the same time, there are limitations on the potential level of protection that contracts can provide. Contract law doctrines are a key limitation, while fair use and other features of copyright law present possible limitations as well.

Even assuming that sophisticated players generate a contract that reflects their ex-ante wishes, the contract's enforceability may be limited. For publishing, this is primarily due to the inability to enforce penalty clauses and the difficulties in calculating damages, though other doctrinal limitations are implicated in other subjects.¹⁰¹ Suppose an author would feel such psychic harm from the publisher making unauthorized distortive edits to the work as to value harm at 100,000 USD but is otherwise willing to work for a fixed payment of 10,000 USD. A court is unlikely to enforce a liquidated damages clause of 100,000 USD due to its disproportionality without special treatment of such right of integrity cases. Specific performance is similarly unavailable except in rare circumstances.

Additionally, demonstrating damages from a breach of moral rights is also difficult and *Zim v. Western Pub. Co.*¹⁰² showcases the potential for finding only nominal damages. Zim was the creator and editor of a series of non-fiction books published by Western Publishing, but decided to reduce his involvement in the series after conflicts with a new Vice-President at Western.¹⁰³ Zim's settlement agreement required that Western "not publish any revision, change, correction, alteration, ... without Zim's prior approval," yet Western published revised

¹⁰¹ Hansmann & Santilli, *Authors' and Artists' Moral Rights*, *supra* note 4 at 120, 142, raises the inability to raise servitudes on property as another limitation in the context of art, but suggests that may be resolved through a license or rental agreement.

¹⁰² *Zim v. W. Pub. Co.*, 573 F.2d 1318 (5th Cir. 1978).

¹⁰³ *Id.* at 1321.

versions of two books without his approval of their submitted changes.¹⁰⁴ While the judge held in favor of Zim on the breach of contract claims, only nominal damages were available as Zim's own statements were the only testimony available for damages.¹⁰⁵ Limitations on damages ultimately limit the potential protections available through contract.

The open doctrinal question¹⁰⁶ of whether parties may contract out of fair use also presents a theoretical limit on the level of potential protections. After all, fair use is widely described to conflict with the moral right of integrity¹⁰⁷ and there is at least one non-contractual situation where fair use has the potential to undesirably limit the application of the right of integrity in publishing – particularly egregious parodies (see *infra* section V.B.2). Hypothetically, a publisher who received the manuscript of an author under an agreement not to publish parodies of the work, could both publish the original as well as edit and release a particularly offensive and critical parody. While this violates the right of integrity, the work may very well be considered fair use such that only contract damages are available, rather than statutory damages or potentially an injunction.

An equally unlikely example potentially arises from the first sale doctrine with respect to the right of attribution. Suppose a person buys a large number of hard copies of a novel, covers the author's name throughout the book, then resells them. This behavior may violate the right of attribution but may be protected under the first sale doctrine if covering the author's name does not result in a derivative work (or alternatively is non-permanent).¹⁰⁸ And contracting out of first sale doctrine by structuring it as a rental may be difficult and unusual in such circumstances.

¹⁰⁴ *Id.* at 1323.

¹⁰⁵ *Id.* at 1326, 1327 note 19. Note however that Zim's claims may be more financially oriented than psychic harms-related due to Zim's demands for a new revisions contract as a condition for approval for one of the books. See *id.* at 1325.

¹⁰⁶ See e.g. Viva R. Moffat, *Super-Copyright: Contracts, Preemption, and the Structure of Copyright Policymaking*, 41 U.C. Davis L. Rev. 45, 45 (2007) (arguing that contracts that do so should be pre-empted by federal law), Guy A. Rub, *Copyright Survives: Rethinking the Copyright-Contract Conflict*, 103 Va. L. Rev. 1141, 1164 (2017) (describing rationale for the no-pre-emption approach). Currently, no pre-emption is the rule in most circuit courts. *Id.* at 1141.

¹⁰⁷ Cathay Y. N. Smith, *Creative Destruction: Copyright's Fair Use Doctrine and the Moral Right of Integrity*, 47 Pepp. L. Rev. 601, 602 (2020) (mentioning "commentators and legislative history [of VARA] doubting the compatibility of fair use with the right of integrity" but concluding that they are compatible)

¹⁰⁸ It is unlikely though possible that this product resale may be a violation of the Lanham Act if the name covering is deemed a false designation of origin. See U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 45-47 (describing the one broad reading of *Dastar* as

The extremeness of such hypotheticals suggest that copyright law limitations are less salient for publishing, though they may be significant for other fields such as photography. Yet in principle, an inability to contract out of fair use places a further ceiling on the level of potential protection similar to that of the non-contractual relation situation, being particularly applicable for the right of integrity. There thus exists doctrinal limits to the degree of contractual protection potentially available.

Ultimately, the strength of contractual protections may vary greatly both between and within industries. Protections, while powerful in theory, are likely more limited in practice by the incomplete text and norms. We now move on to the issue of breadth of coverage by contract.

C. Breadth of coverage by contract

The amount of contractual coverage is generally limited in publishing to the publisher-author relationship. As a general matter, however, there is significant variation by field or industry, with little to no coverage in fields such as french cooking or stand-up comedy,¹⁰⁹ to far greater coverage in fields such as software. There may be little coverage by contract even when coverage by contract is feasible and desirable, as with a subset of work done for employers / contractors (other work such as ghostwriting will have moral rights explicitly accounted for). Here, norms instead govern the relationship.¹¹⁰ Although a weakness of moral rights effectuated by contract seemingly involves the limited number of parties covered by the terms,¹¹¹ this is not necessarily the case.

being “premised on the false designation of the origin of ideas, concepts, or communications embodied in tangible goods,” and thus leading to the rejection of claims of non-attribution, but also that there are courts which take a narrower interpretation including one interpretation that *Dastar* only applies to public domain works.). Cf. *Dastar Corp. v. Twentieth Cent. Fox Film Corp.*, 539 U.S. 23, 23-24 (2003) (Plaintiff’s false designation of origin claim “would undoubtedly be sustained if [defendant] had bought some of [plaintiff’s] videotapes and merely repackaged them as its own.”).

¹⁰⁹ See *supra* note 49.

¹¹⁰ See Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 85 - 88 (discussing norms in the employment context).

¹¹¹ Bechtold & Engel, *The Valuation of Moral Rights*, *supra* note 4 at 25 (raising concern of privity), Hansmann & Santilli, *Authors' and Artists' Moral Rights*, *supra* note 4 at 101 (same), The U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 136-37 (describing privity problem but noting ability to structure licenses to affect all downstream users as with CC licenses or licenses with “rights that carry through to any sublicensees”),

After all, contracts may be phrased so as to cover the entire population as with Creative Commons (CC) licenses. The fact that CC licenses are offered to every reuser subjects every reuser to its terms of attribution (and potentially other conditions), an approach that has been called “America’s moral rights?” by Sundara Rajan. Yet while Sundara Rajan describes the potential limits of the system as a choice for the American author between moral rights and economic rights,¹¹² one can conceive of licenses that allow for both.

Here, the cases of *Great Minds v. FedEx office* and *Great Minds v. Office Depot* showcases both the limitations of a Creative Commons Attribution Noncommercial License, as well as the potential for a differently worded license to better protect the creator’s commercial interests. In *FedEx office*, the non-profit organization Great Minds distributed a copyrighted math curriculum digitally under a Noncommercial license (while selling physical copies), then sued FedEx when the office printed copies of the textbook on behalf of schools.¹¹³ The suit was dismissed as the court held that school districts were allowed to use third parties when exercising rights under the CC license. Upon the *FedEx office* ruling, Office depot (another print shop), which had initially entered into a licensing agreement with Great Minds to print physical copies, decided to terminate the agreement, bringing about the second lawsuit which Office Depot won.¹¹⁴ While Great Minds ultimately failed to sell its curriculum due to such rulings, a differently phrased license would have enabled their business model of selling physical copies — while maintaining the moral rights benefits of attribution. Thus the trade-off of moral rights and economics rights is not so straightforward.

What exists may instead be a trade-off between the breadth of contractual coverage and the strength of economic or moral rights retained. While the use of clickwrap / shrinkwrap contracts may enable the coverage of a large number of people (even if not to the extent of Creative Commons licenses), one eventually reaches the doctrinal limits within contract law, doctrines such as unconscionability. After all, a contract of adhesion that affects anyone who utilizes the content, without any opportunity for negotiation, is likely procedurally

¹¹² Mira T. Sundara Rajan, *Creative Commons: America's Moral Rights?*, 21 Fordham Intell. Prop. Media & Ent. L.J. 905, 967 (2011).

¹¹³ *Great Minds v. Fedex Off. & Print Servs., Inc.*, 886 F.3d 91, 93 (2d Cir. 2018).

¹¹⁴ *Great Minds v. Off. Depot, Inc.*, 945 F.3d 1106, 1109 (9th Cir. 2019). Creative Commons intervened in support of Office Depot. *Id.* at 1107.

unconscionable.¹¹⁵ The fact that CC licenses offer the content up for free may thus be a strike against substantive unconscionability, supporting the licenses' enforcement.

Yet while there is the potential for broad coverage in contracts within the publishing industry, as a general matter, the breadth of coverage may also be limited by the law. After all, the law actively prevents the existence of contracts in specific relationships such as in the production of music covers, where compulsory licensing allows anyone to make a cover so long as they pay a modest royalty.¹¹⁶ At least for music, this approach forecloses the ability to effectuate a right of integrity via contract. Here, statute places us outside the contractual relationship and specifically governs this non-contractual relationship. Though not currently applicable to publishing, any inefficient lack of moral rights in such circumstances may only be resolved by a statutory moral rights system.

Contracts ultimately have the potential for broad and powerful coverage. This potential, while supported by norms, is limited both doctrinally and by issues of industry structure / standards. Thus contractual coverage is ultimately complementary to the other laws that protect non-contractual relations.

V. NON-CONTRACTUAL RELATIONS

Generally, the ability to duplicate the efficient outcome of moral rights also depends on non-contractual relations: both with norms and where other laws provide incidental protection through the coverage of re-use cases.

A. Role of (non-contract-space) Norms

Recognizing the effect of norms on the level of protection in the non-contractual context, this paper emphasizes the potentially powerful enforcement of sanctions against plagiarism¹¹⁷ within specific groups. The norms based response to plagiarism is most salient in academic environments, though may appear even in

¹¹⁵ See § 18:10. Elements of unconscionability—Procedural and substantive unconscionability, 8 Williston on Contracts § 18:10 (4th ed.)

¹¹⁶ E.g. 17 U.S.C. § 115.

¹¹⁷ While plagiarism emphasizes attribution, a key distinction between it and the moral right of attribution involves the potential need to credit the originator of ideas with plagiarism.

casual online contexts.¹¹⁸ Most straightforwardly, students who plagiarize are sanctioned by their schools, leading to possible expulsion. The response to academics plagiarizing one another is more complex, involving action both by journal editors as well as the academic institution. Retraction Watch is a helpful blog on this front.¹¹⁹ Journal editors have retracted articles due to plagiarism, banning the author from the journal for years,¹²⁰ and schools have demoted researchers for repeated plagiarism.¹²¹ Individual authors have also resigned in particularly embarrassing situations.¹²² In a situation of research collaboration, a university press has even granted co-authorship credit in response to the complaint of a graduate student on passages being used without attribution.¹²³

In fact, the potential need to credit the originator of ideas with plagiarism may actually generate a stronger level of protection than moral rights would for academic works. After all, to the extent that moral rights protection is also subject to the idea-facts-expression distinction, historical and scientific work may receive limited protection. The fact that plagiarism norms may continue to protect historians / scientists' attribution interests without allowing them to make economic claims on facts and ideas reflects the potential strength of a norms-based system.

Yet the norms-based nature of such protection results in a wide array of responses to misbehavior, including a journal's potential decision to correct a paper for "errors" rather than label the issue plagiarism and retract it. Delays on both

¹¹⁸ For example, there is shaming through criticisms of "reposts" on sites such as Reddit. James Meese, "*It Belongs to the Internet*": *Animal Images, Attribution Norms and the Politics of Amateur Media Production*, 17(2) *M/C Journal* (2014).

¹¹⁹ Cf. What people are saying about Retraction Watch, Retraction Watch, n.d. <https://retractionwatch.com/what-people-are-saying-about-retraction-watch/> (collection of quotes praising Retraction Watch).

¹²⁰ Ivan Oransky, Plagiarism of a thesis earns authors a retraction — and a two-year-publishing ban, Retraction Watch, October 27, 2021, <https://retractionwatch.com/2021/10/27/plagiarism-of-a-thesis-earns-authors-a-retraction-and-a-two-year-publishing-ban/>

¹²¹ Adam Marcus, Researcher in Japan suspended, demoted for plagiarism, Retraction Watch, August 09, 2021, <https://retractionwatch.com/2021/08/09/researcher-in-japan-suspended-demoted-for-plagiarism/>

¹²² Adam Marcus, Columbia historian stepping down after plagiarism finding, Retraction Watch, September 17, 2019, <https://retractionwatch.com/2019/09/17/columbia-historian-stepping-down-after-plagiarism-finding/>. (findings of more than 50 instances of plagiarism actually led to a withdrawal of a prize for the work).

¹²³ Adam Marcus, Obama intelligence official shortchanged grad student in 2015 book, Retraction Watch, September 09, 2021, <https://retractionwatch.com/2021/09/09/obama-intelligence-official-shortchanged-grad-student-in-2015-book/>

retractions and corrections are also common.¹²⁴ This choice not to retract is controversial, and editorial advisory board members have even resigned in the face of their journal's initial decision not to retract an article that allegedly re-worded much of another paper.¹²⁵ The results of investigations by institutions may be similarly controversial. A research organization's investigations report once differentiated “‘plagiarism properly so called’ from ‘unacknowledged borrowings’,”¹²⁶ though the subject of the investigation was ultimately dismissed.¹²⁷ Similarly, even where the subject of the investigation ultimately resigns after years of controversy, the victim of plagiarism does not necessarily receive compensation, as shown in the investigation of a now-former Columbia historian:

Although the investigation vindicated [the victim], it wasn't a total victory. The university's standing committee, in its final report, overruled recommendations from the investigating body that would have awarded [the

¹²⁴ Michael Dougherty, A two-year drama: The anatomy of a retraction request, Retraction Watch, June 30, 2020, <https://retractionwatch.com/2020/06/30/a-two-year-drama-the-anatomy-of-a-retraction-request/>

¹²⁵ There was an initial resigning board member from the same institution as the victim and the journal ultimately retracted the article after additional professors (mostly from the same institution) resigned from the editorial advisory board. Mark Zastrow, Board member resigns from journal over handling of paper accused of plagiarism, Retraction Watch, October 10, 2017, <https://retractionwatch.com/2017/10/10/board-member-resigns-journal-handling-paper-accused-plagiarism/>. Alison McCook, Journal to assemble “senior editorial committee” to review paper that led to board resignations, Retraction Watch, November 10, 2017, <http://retractionwatch.com/2017/11/10/journal-assemble-senior-editorial-committee-review-paper-led-board-resignations/>, Rong Wang, Yong Xu & Bin Liu, *Retraction Note: Recombination spot identification Based on gapped k-mers*, 8 Scientific Reports (2018).

Note that public pressure leading to retraction is not always the result and that the idiosyncratic nature of editor governed retractions can even create awkward situations where the journal refuses to retract even when a non-plagiarising co-author asks for an article withdrawal due to plagiarism claims. Ivan Oransky, ‘This is really ridiculous’: An author admitted plagiarism. His supervisor asked for a retraction. The publisher said, “nah.”, Retraction Watch, January 03, 2022, <https://retractionwatch.com/2022/01/03/this-is-really-ridiculous-an-author-admitted-plagiarism-his-supervisor-asked-for-a-retraction-the-publisher-said-nah/>

¹²⁶ Ivan Oransky, ‘A fig leaf that doesn't quite cover up’: Commission says philosopher engaged in ‘unacknowledged borrowings’ but not plagiarism, Retraction Watch, June 28, 2021, <https://retractionwatch.com/2021/06/28/a-fig-leaf-that-doesnt-quite-cover-up-commission-says-philosopher-engaged-in-unacknowledged-borrowings-but-not-plagiarism/>

¹²⁷ Justin Weinberg, CNRS Commission Defends Roques in Response to Plagiarism Accusations / Update: Roques Dismissed from CNRS (updated), Daily Nous, June 26, 2021, <https://dailynous.com/2021/06/26/cnrs-defends-roques-in-response-to-plagiarism-accusations/>

victim] \$25,000 in research funding as compensation for his efforts pushing the misconduct case and for the potential hit to his “academic reputation.” It also rejected the recommendation that [the plagiarizer] be ordered to formally acknowledge his misdeeds to [the victim].¹²⁸

Thus, not only do norms generate idiosyncratic results, but the remedies and compensatory mechanisms may also be limited relative to a hypothetical cause of action enforceable through the court system.

Such idiosyncrisms reflect power dynamics within academia. One article describes as “competitive plagiarism” the strategy of “some established scholars” to take ideas from others’ unpublished papers and fast track to publish their own version.¹²⁹ Much of the anecdotal evidence on corrections rather than retractions further involves more established researchers plagiarizing from the articles, dissertations, or informal works of less well-known ones.¹³⁰ The power dynamic is more explicit with graduate students and professors, with certain graduate students reporting plagiarism of their work by a professor in a position of power in their institution.¹³¹ Similarly, power dynamics can determine whose name is credited as author at the first instance in collaborative relationships between professors and graduate students.¹³²

Thus while academia’s norms of attribution may effectuate moral rights more effectively for established scholars, it is unclear whether improved effectuation for such scholars translates to greater incentives to create as a whole for them. After all, the decreased applicability of sanctions against them may generate a

¹²⁸ Marcus, *Columbia historian stepping down*, *supra* note 122.

¹²⁹ Brian Martin, *Plagiarism, misrepresentation, and exploitation by established professionals: power and tactics* in HANDBOOK OF ACADEMIC INTEGRITY 913, 915 (T. Bretag ed. 2016). See also Syed Shahabuddin, *Plagiarism in Academia*, 21(3) International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education 353 (2009) (describing various situations from lenient treatment of academics, to institutional cover-ups).

¹³⁰ See e.g. Oransky, *publisher said nah*, *supra* note 125 (only issuing correction and explicitly mentioning reputation of well-known innocent co-authors), Anonymous academic, *Plagiarism is rife in academia, so why is it rarely acknowledged?*, The Guardian, October 27, 2017, <https://www.theguardian.com/higher-education-network/2017/oct/27/plagiarism-is-rife-in-academia-so-why-is-it-rarely-acknowledged> (the anonymous academic author copied by a senior professor, with only a correction being issued), cf., Zastrow, *Board member resigns*, *supra* note 125 (co-author of plagiarising work was board member of journal and correction was initially issued rather than retraction until mass resignations occurred).

¹³¹ Becker, *Graduate students’ experiences*, *supra* note 29 at 257 (Table 1).

¹³² Fisk, *Credit Where It's Due*, *supra* note 4 at 102.

substitution effect, with the opportunity to plagiarize crowding out some incentives for original scholarship.

Such issues in both enforcement as well as remedies reflect the limitations of norms. Thus norms, while potentially helpful, may not necessarily substitute for the deterrence effects of actionable legal protection. Recognizing the potential protections afforded by norms in the non-contractual front, we move on to the sources of legal protection in the space.

B. Protection through incidental coverage by Copyright (alongside other laws)

The relative effectiveness of contracts in producing moral rights depends much on the incidental coverage of the non-contractual re-use situations by other laws. Here, perfect coverage by powerful other laws in conjunction with an enforceable well-specified contract produces, in practice, a similar result to statutory moral rights.¹³³ Legal arguments available may include state claims such as defamation (e.g. attribution to a distorted work where reputation is harmed)¹³⁴ as well as the right of publicity (e.g. misattribution).¹³⁵ Unfair competition is another potential argument (e.g. consumers may be confused regarding the origin of an altered work as being the author's or vice versa), if it is not preempted by copyright law.¹³⁶ Given the potential limitations of those alternative avenues, however, this article emphasizes federal law, particularly the role of copyright infringement as a form of incidental protection.

¹³³ Suppose there is a painting that was never shown to the public (assume no or waived VARA), sold to someone who credibly agrees to lock it in a vault. A third party who attempts to violate the right of integrity will at the first instance face criminal sanctions for breaking and entering.

¹³⁴ The U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 108, notes however that “defamation law is relevant to only a small sub-set of fact patterns under which an author’s attribution or integrity interests may be impacted.”

¹³⁵ While the U.S. Copyright Office states that the right “has continued to be an important mechanism for protecting the moral rights of authors”, *id.* at 112, it has recognized the right’s limitations in situations of non-attribution, copyright preemption, as well as with state law idiosyncrasies, *id.* at 112-116.

¹³⁶ See e.g. 104 N.Y. Jur. 2d Trade Regulation § 249 (pre-emption if claim “grounded solely in the defendant’s copying of copyrighted expression.”). § 18:47. Unfair competition, including passing off and reverse passing off, 6 Patry on Copyright § 18:47. The Copyright Office has further noted that “outcomes under state unfair competition law differ little from outcomes under the Supreme Court’s interpretation of the Lanham Act in *Dastar*,” thus limiting the applicability of the approach. U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 108.

Much of the non-contractual re-use situations are otherwise covered by exclusive rights of the author such that a copyright infringement suit may be brought.¹³⁷ This practically covers much ground in not only publishing but also other works such as film. While the U.S. Copyright Office has emphasized the role of the Section 106(2) derivative works right as protecting the right of integrity,¹³⁸ both it as well as the Section 106(1) reproduction right further protect the right of attribution. After all, copyright protection is the principle behind the function of Creative Commons licenses, which have clauses automatically revoking the license where its requirements are not followed.

Though often cited for its analysis of moral rights under the Lanham Act, *Gilliam v. American Broadcasting Companies, Inc.*¹³⁹ also showcases the ability to enforce moral rights through copyright litigation. The plaintiffs, Monty Python, had created the popular “Monty Python’s Flying Circus” program for the BBC, who licensed the recordings to Time-Life films in the US.¹⁴⁰ Monty Python retained all rights in the script, and the BBC only had the authority to alter the script prior to recording.¹⁴¹ However, BBC’s agreement with Time-Life films allowed Time-Life to edit the programs to add ads and censor content, and Time-Life agreed with ABC for ABC to broadcast a version of the special that cut 24 minutes from a 90 minute program.¹⁴²

Monty Python, offended by the mutilating nature of the cuts, was eventually able to obtain a preliminary injunction. The court stated that the edits made by ABC exceeded the scope of BBC’s license with Monty Python, concluding that there is

¹³⁷ For now, abstract away the agency problem that arises where the author no longer holds the copyright to the work. See infra section V.B.4 for a discussion of such issues.

¹³⁸ U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, supra note 6 at 102 (“Section 106(2) has regularly been cited as providing a right of integrity for copyright owners.”). See also, Deidré A. Keller, *Recognizing the Derivative Works Right As A Moral Right: A Case Comparison and Proposal*, 63 Case W. Res. L. Rev. 511, 515 (2012) (stating that courts enforce moral rights “in the guise of enforcing the derivative works right” and analyzing the *Gone with the Wind* and *The Catcher in the Rye* cases that implicate the right of integrity), and Erin E. Gallagher, note, *On the Fair Use Fence Between Derivative Works and Allegedly Infringing Creations: A Proposal for A Middle Ground*, 80 Notre Dame L. Rev. 759, 771 (2005) (criticizing “Courts’ backdoor accommodation of moral rights” through the derivative works right through cases that implicate the right of integrity). Roberta Rosenthal Kwall, *Copyright and the Moral Right: Is an American Marriage Possible?*, 38 Vand. L. Rev. 1, 64 (1985) (positively portraying the ability to sue on this front).

¹³⁹ *Gilliam v. Am. Broad. Companies, Inc.*, 538 F.2d 14 (2d Cir. 1976).

¹⁴⁰ *Id.* at 17.

¹⁴¹ *Id.*

¹⁴² *Id.* at 18.

a substantial likelihood that Monty Python will successfully prove infringement.¹⁴³ The ownership of the copyright is the difference between Monty Python's enforcement of the right of integrity here and Zyla's failure to enforce the right of attribution for her contributions to the textbook, *supra*. Thus, copyright infringement suits present an opportunity to enforce moral rights in publishing.

1. Limitations from Copyright's Doctrinal Features

Yet the use of copyright infringement to enforce moral rights is limited by copyright's doctrinal features. Such limits include the idea-facts-expression distinction, the thinness of copyright for a particular work (especially relevant for other types of works such as photos and compilations), the doctrine associated with joint works, as well as the open-ended, potentially far reaching, fair use inquiry.

The idea-facts-expression distinction limits the protections afforded to historical and scientific works, with historical events being facts. Certain expressions such as some descriptions of mathematical models may also be excluded from copyright by the merger doctrine.¹⁴⁴ While scientific text itself may be a form of expression, protection is less likely to extend to nonliteral copying. This has the result of both limiting opportunities for enforcing attribution to mostly literal copying as well as potentially barring the enforcement of the right of integrity. This issue is unlikely to apply to fiction, and strong norms in academia may mitigate this issue for more senior researchers. However, a hypothetical statutory moral rights system that subjects historical and scientific works to protection would generate superior results for the junior researchers less able to take advantage of norms.

The joint work rules are another source of problematic results when applied to infringement suits based on co-authorship disputes between collaborators (who do not have contracts due to norms). After all, while infringement lawsuits are likely available based on a copying claim over individual contributions,¹⁴⁵ the situation

¹⁴³ *Id.* at 23. The court goes on to state that Monty Python would have won anyways due to the Lanham act. *Id.* at 23-24.

¹⁴⁴ See *Seng-Tiong Ho v. Taflove*, 648 F.3d 489, 489 (7th Cir. 2011) (holding that plaintiffs' unpublished mathematical models taken by defendants were not subject to copyright). However, the decision also suggested that the plaintiffs were particularly inept, both in filing the wrong motion, *id.* at 495, and in failing to submit timely counter arguments on the defense's merger argument. *Id.* at 500.

¹⁴⁵ See e.g. *Thomson v. Larson*, 147 F.3d 195, 206 (2d Cir. 1998) (explaining that Thomson may be able to claim an interest in her contributions to the musical "Rent", even if there is no unity of

becomes more complicated if a joint work is found with respect to a particular version of a given work. Because of the joint author's right to prepare individual derivative works,¹⁴⁶ moral rights enforcement through copyright is unavailable where a joint author later self-plagiarizes for a solo work, choosing not to credit the initial co-author.

The situation is only slightly less problematic if a co-author is cut out of the revised version of an article they initially co-authored. While it may be possible to file for a declaratory judgment of co-authorship,¹⁴⁷ it is difficult to meet the requirement of unity of intent on the subsequent work if a disagreement had occurred between authors.¹⁴⁸ Yet even if the court finds a joint authorship, the right of attribution may only be available indirectly if at all (perhaps through complaining to various third parties) given individual authors' ability to exploit the work. And the right of integrity will be non-existent.¹⁴⁹

Germany and France's more personality rights influenced approach to joint authorship better facilitates moral rights. After all, in both Germany and France, mutual agreement is necessary to exercise exclusive rights in the work.¹⁵⁰ This

intent to create a joint work). Prof. Kwall sees the loss of Thomson's joint authorship claims as a disadvantage of enforcing the right of attribution through copyright. Roberta Rosenthal Kwall, *The Attribution Right in the United States: Caught in the Crossfire Between Copyright and Section 43(a)*, 77 Wash. L. Rev. 985, 990, 1001 (2002). This concern is real, though may be overstated given Thomson's subsequent success in obtaining front page billing as dramaturg (though not author), as well as the specific facts of the case with Larson's unlikely and untimely passing.

¹⁴⁶ E.g. *Weissmann v. Freeman*, 868 F.2d 1313, 1316 (2d Cir. 1989) (finding that the subsequent work of a co-author was an individual derivative work despite the fact that "portions of [the work] w[as] taken virtually verbatim from prior jointly authored pieces....").

¹⁴⁷ *Mallon v. Marshall*, 95 F. Supp. 3d 274, 277 (D. Mass. 2015) (denying a motion to dismiss against a request for declaratory judgment request on co-authorship as plaintiff had alleged "that he co-authored the paper that went on to be published" without attribution).

¹⁴⁸ While plaintiff survived the 12(b)(6) motion, the court went on to grant summary judgment for the defendant as the plaintiff later clarified that he desired solely the article's retraction rather than attribution long before the lawsuit began, with the court holding that this objective reflects the loss of the intent to create a joint work. *Mallon v. Marshall*, 224 F. Supp. 3d 97, 102 (D. Mass. 2016). The court also mentioned that the existence of the paper "in a version that Dr. Mallon no longer wished to see published," reflects the loss of the "unified, integrated 'whole'" Id. at 102.

¹⁴⁹ See Roberta Rosenthal Kwall, *Moral Rights for University Employees and Students: Can Educational Institutions Do Better Than the U.S. Copyright Law?*, 27 J.C. & U.L. 53, 70 (2000) ("[N]o [legal] remedy exists for a joint author when his fellow joint authors publish his work in an altered, or objectionable, state.").

¹⁵⁰ See French Intellectual Property Code [Article L113-3](#) ("Joint authors must exercise their rights by mutual agreement.") (Machine translation), German Copyright Law [Section 8\(2\)](#) ("The joint authors are jointly entitled to the right to publish and exploit the work; Changes to the work are only

avoids much of the attribution and integrity problems that arise from independent exploitation, even without explicit moral rights statutes. Given the potentially high economic costs of mutual agreement however, the American approach may remain optimal. So too might the problematic (on the moral rights front) joint authorship rules be seen as a desirable penalty default for contracting by sophisticated parties. Perhaps a narrowly tailored statutory moral rights system may then be the best of both worlds.

2. Fair Use Limitations

Fair use is a more general limitation, with more expansive interpretations reducing the incidental level of protection afforded by copyright law. Fair use's practical implications to trade book publishing of fiction (as opposed to other fields) is not currently substantial, given fiction's status at the core of copyright. However, the potential for expansive readings of fair use to disrupt moral rights enforcement through contracts and the copyright system is most straightforwardly reflected in the line of copyleft troll cases in photography. There, fair use impedes the enforcement of attribution through creative commons licenses.

Copyleft trolls refer to those who offer their works online through a copyleft license (mostly the creative commons licenses) with the objective of suing people who reuse the work without following the license requirements so as to obtain judgments or settlements.¹⁵¹ *Philpot v. Media Research Center Inc.*¹⁵² is an example of courts striking back against the trolls through holdings of fair use. The copyleft troll Philpot¹⁵³ had uploaded a photo of Kenny Chesney to Wikimedia Commons (a free and open media repository) under a CC attribution license that requires only attribution.¹⁵⁴ Media Research Center ("MRC"), which operates a conservative values website, took the photo without attribution and used it in its articles.¹⁵⁵ They

permitted with the consent of the co-authors. However, a co-author may not refuse his consent to publication, exploitation or modification in bad faith." (Machine translation).

¹⁵¹ E.g. *Philpot v. L.M. Commc'ns II of S.C., Inc.*, 343 F. Supp. 3d 694, 697-98 (E.D. Ky. 2018) (defendant did not attribute and thus lost on summary judgment).

¹⁵² *Philpot v. Media Rsch. Ctr. Inc.*, 279 F. Supp. 3d 708 (E.D. Va. 2018) (holding fair use on a photo of Kenny Chesney and Kid Rock on summary judgment).

¹⁵³ A photographer who has filed over 150 lawsuits for improper reuse of his often stock photo-esque photos. Daxton Stewart, *Rise of the Copyleft Trolls: When Photographers Sue After Creative Commons Licenses Go Awry*, 2 (August 22, 2007) (unpublished manuscript) (available on SSRN https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3844180).

¹⁵⁴ *Media Rsch. Ctr. Inc.*, 279 F. Supp. 3d at 711.

¹⁵⁵ *Id.*

placed the Chesney Photograph in the context of an article that discusses his pro-life music. The court controversially¹⁵⁶ granted summary judgment to the MRC on fair use grounds, holding that use of the photos in the articles were transformative due to its purpose of news reporting and political commentary, and that there was no economic market for the free photographs.¹⁵⁷ Such a decision may, at least in part, come from the courts' attempts to penalize Philpot's bad behavior.¹⁵⁸ Yet it is fair use analysis' non-consideration of attribution that ultimately results in this decision that limits the strength of incidental protection from copyright.

Here, a comparison with the Israeli courts' approach to fair use showcases the benefits of a statutory moral rights system that explicitly considers the right of attribution. Israel's current fair use doctrine is based off of the American one and interpreted nearly identically with the exception of the addition of attribution considerations.¹⁵⁹ The consideration of attribution began before Israel's shift to a fair use system (from a fair dealing system) with a remark in *Eisenman v. Qimron*, in which the court suggested in dicta that there was no fair dealing defense for the reprinting of deciphered dead sea scrolls without permission due to the lack of attribution.¹⁶⁰ While this dicta-derived court incorporation of attribution into the fair use analysis is criticized by Israeli scholars,¹⁶¹ the likely existence of Israeli

¹⁵⁶ Keith Kupferschmid, Copyright Law in 2018: Top 10 Court Cases, Copyright Clearance Center, January 18, 2019, <https://www.copyright.com/blog/copyright-law-in-2018-top-10-court-cases/> (using the case as one of the examples of a district court "botch[ing] the fair use analysis."), Stephen Carlisle, Has This Court Decision Rendered the Creative Commons License Unenforceable?, Nova Southeastern University, January 19, 2018, <http://copyright.nova.edu/creative-commons-license/> (suggesting that the court's holding "effectively render[s] the Creative Commons license ineffective and unenforceable.").

¹⁵⁷ *Media Rsch. Ctr. Inc.*, 279 F. Supp. 3d, at 719.

¹⁵⁸ A court has literally labeled Philpot and his lawyer "'copyright' trolls". *Philpot v. Emmis Operating Co.*, No. 1:18-CV-00816-RP, 2019 WL 2928774, 2 (W.D. Tex. July 8, 2019).

¹⁵⁹ Lital Helman, *Session IV: Fair Use and Other Exceptions*, 40 Colum J.L. & Arts 395, 398-99 (2017).

¹⁶⁰ Dead Sea Scrolls Case para. 20 ("I cannot accept this argument. Appellants published the deciphered text in its entirety, without mentioning Qimron's name, and by this they knowingly infringed his right to be the first to publish the deciphered text.") (unofficially translated by Michael Birnhack, <https://www.tau.ac.il/law/members/birnhack/DSSstransaltion.pdf>). Note that the Israeli court's holding of copyrightability in the first place was criticized in American scholarship. Kwall, *Caught in the Crossfire*, *supra* note 145 at note 61 (citing scholarship). To the extent that moral rights are desirable in this context, as Prof. Kwall assumes, *id.* at 995, the lack of copyrightability would be a limitation of the idea-expression distinction discussed *supra*.

¹⁶¹ Helman, *Session IV*, *supra* note 159 at 399 note 38 (citing Michael Birnhack for critique of the trend).

cases that may be fair use if not for the lack of attribution showcases an area that contracts-based moral rights fail to cover.

It is possible, though unlikely, that a non-attributing work of text may otherwise come under fair use (rather than another limitation such as merger doctrine).¹⁶² After all, the situation in *Eisenman v. Qimron* did not constitute fair dealing on other grounds.¹⁶³ Yet while the fair use exception to the right of attribution is more likely implicated in photography than publishing, a potentially more salient situation involves the sophisticated trade book author's enforcement of the right of integrity¹⁶⁴ against fanfiction and parody.

Authors attitudes to fan fiction varies significantly,¹⁶⁵ and some such as Sharon Lee describe significant psychological ties to their characters.¹⁶⁶ Fan fiction that alters characters or places them in new contexts thus has the potential to distort and mutilate.¹⁶⁷ Under current doctrine, authors may be able to enforce their right of integrity through copyright as imitative fanfiction's use of existing characters may constitute a prima facie case of copyright infringement. Fans apparently described the author Anne Rice as sending lawyers, and J.K. Rowling had sent a cease and desist to a website as well.¹⁶⁸ Whether fans may defend their works as a fair use is an open question, though the potentially strong arguments for fair use with non-commercial fan works¹⁶⁹ is countered in practice by such fan authors' difficulties

¹⁶² Perhaps verbatim copying of a thought experiment for educational purposes without attribution.

¹⁶³ Dead Sea scrolls case, *supra* note 160, para. 20.

¹⁶⁴ Trade authors' enforcement of right of integrity has been discussed by Gallagher, note, *On the Fair Use Fence*, *supra* 138 at 760 (discussing the Cat in the Hat as well as the Gone with the Wind cases), as well as Keller, *Derivative Works Right As a Moral Right*, *supra* 138 at 512 (analyzing the Gone with the Wind and The Catcher in the Rye cases).

¹⁶⁵ Professional Author Fanfic Policies, Fanlore, https://fanlore.org/wiki/Professional_Author_Fanfic_Policies (fan site listing positions of various authors).

¹⁶⁶ Sharon Lee, The second answer, October 26, 2013, <http://sharonleewriter.com/2013/10/the-second-answer/>

¹⁶⁷ See also Grace Westcott, Friction over Fan Fiction: Is this burgeoning art form legal?, *Literary Review of Canada* (July-August 2008), https://reviewcanada.ca/magazine/2008/07/friction-over-fan-fiction/?fbclid=IwAR3Tq3iy2nQ739d_KxrlwwLeawZW0r8j7ReezbNhhmKPGUf3AjUAKcEUIcU

¹⁶⁸ Gita Jackson, It Used To Be Perilous To Write Fanfiction, *Kotaku*, May 16, 2018, <https://kotaku.com/it-used-to-be-perilous-to-write-fanfiction-1826083509>

¹⁶⁹ Rebecca Tushnet, *Legal Fictions: Copyright, Fan Fiction, and a New Common Law*, 17 *Loy. L.A. Ent. L. Rev.* 651, 654 (1997), Michelle Chatelain, *Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Copyright Law: Fan Fiction, Derivative Works, and the Fair Use Doctrine*, 15 *Tul. J. Tech. & Intell. Prop.*

defending themselves in lawsuits (due to the sizeable costs). Works of parody, which comments on or critiques the author, presents a more legally salient problem. Parodies are largely protected by fair use in America (and international equivalents elsewhere). Yet they potentially conflict with the integrity right as a parody is “by its very nature, a ‘distortion’ of another work.”¹⁷⁰

France, which has both the right of integrity and a parody exception, attempts to draw a distinction between the two. They limit the parody exception to works that “satisfy the rules of the genre [of parody].”¹⁷¹ And scholars have conceived of at least some circumstances where moral rights would be violated by parody in the UK and Australia.¹⁷² The US’s lack of moral rights prevents this analysis, with fair use analysis ironically supporting more critical work that is more likely to violate the right of integrity: the particularly egregious parody.¹⁷³

Thus, while plaintiffs can effectuate something approaching the right of integrity in cases such as *Dr. Seuss Enterprises, L.P. v. Penguin Books USA, Inc.* against an imitative parody that uses the Dr. Seuss style to describe the O.J. Simpson trial,¹⁷⁴ the limits of incidental protection is shown with *Suntrust Bank v.*

199, 212 (2012) (arguing that non-commercial works should be fan fiction but suggesting that a circuit split may impede the adoption of the reasoning.).

¹⁷⁰ SABINE JACQUES, THE PARODY EXCEPTION IN COPYRIGHT LAW 168 (2019) (Chapter 6, Parody and Moral Rights). See also Moana Weir, *Making Sense of Copyright Law Relating to Parody: A Moral Rights Perspective*, 18 Monash U. L. Rev. 194, 196 (1992) (“In cases of true parody, . . . , the rights relevant to the issue of infringement are the author’s moral rights of integrity, honour and reputation”).

Both Gallagher and Keller raised the issue of fair use parodies in their discussion of enforcement through the derivative works right, Gallagher note, *On the Fair Use Fence*, *supra* note 138 at 766 (calling the 9th Cir.’s decision that *The Cat Not in the Hat* was not a parody a “blunder” for not seeing Fair use as a fence), Keller, *Derivative Works Right As a Moral Right*, *supra* note 138 at 534 (noting the holding that *The Wind Done Gone* was a parody).

¹⁷¹ JACQUES, THE PARODY EXCEPTION, *supra* note 170 at 189. See also, Alexandra Giannopoulou, Parody in France, report for COMMUNIA, 8 (2016) (“hate parody” not encompassed within the exception).

¹⁷² See e.g. Dinusha Mendis & Martin Kretschmer, The Treatment of Parodies under Copyright Law in Seven Jurisdictions: A Comparative Review of the Underlying Principles, UK Intellectual Property Office, 51 Note 196 (2013) (independent commissioned [report](#)) (“Still others claim . . . that the author’s moral right will only be infringed where the parody is ‘offensive to the spirit of the original work’.”). JACQUES, THE PARODY EXCEPTION, *supra* note 170 at 192 (describing a hypothetical lawsuit on a real Australian cartoonist’s use of an “aged Tintin-esque character to depict” an Australian politician”).

¹⁷³ Cf. Dane S. Ciolino, *Rethinking the Compatibility of Moral Rights and Fair Use*, 54 Wash. & Lee L. Rev. 33, 85 (1997) (describing the difficulties of applying the “transformative use” standard to VARA infringements due to the greater damage to the work).

¹⁷⁴ *Dr. Seuss Enterprises, L.P. v. Penguin Books USA, Inc.*, 109 F.3d 1394 (9th Cir. 1997)

*Houghton Mifflin Co.*¹⁷⁵ Dr. Seuss Enterprises argued, alongside actual copyright infringement arguments, that they “reject[ed] any requests for use of the copyrights and trademarks which would, in any way, tarnish the reputation and ideals of the works and their author Ted Geisel [(Dr. Seuss)].”¹⁷⁶ And because the parody did not criticize or comment on Dr. Seuss, it was held not to be fair use.¹⁷⁷ Protecting Dr. Seuss Enterprises’ economic interests incidentally protected its moral ones.¹⁷⁸

Yet *Suntrust Bank v. Houghton Mifflin Co.*¹⁷⁹ showcases the limits of this approach. After all, the case is a situation where explicit right of integrity analysis would be beneficial, even if the result of allowing the work may be identical. The defendant had appropriated “the characters, settings, and plot twists” of *Gone with the Wind* (*GWTW*) by Margaret Mitchell in their parody, *The Wind Done Gone* (*TWGD*).¹⁸⁰ And with “an intense desire to retain control over the perception of Mitchell’s literary legacy” against a work that “openly address[es] Mitchell’s racist undertones,” Mitchell’s estate sued.¹⁸¹ The court favorably described *TWGD* as “a critical statement that seeks to rebut and destroy the perspective, judgments, and mythology of *GWTW*” as a part of fair use’s purpose and character analysis.¹⁸² Yet this was balanced against the economic interests of *GWTW*’s sales rather than the reputational rationale behind the lawsuit — a limit to effectuating moral rights through copyright. It is the US’s lack of moral rights analysis that ultimately enables the court to avoid confronting the reputational interests head on, a direct

¹⁷⁵ *Suntrust Bank v. Houghton Mifflin Co.*, 268 F.3d 1257 (11th Cir. 2001). While the U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *Supra* note 6 at 102-03 mentions that *Dr. Seuss Enterprises v. Penguin Books USA, Inc.* and *Suntrust Bank v. Houghton Mifflin Co.* “illustrate the interaction between moral rights/derivative works claims and fair use”, its commentary is limited to the fact that qualifying as a parody leads to the upholding of the parody defense.

¹⁷⁶ Appelle Answering Brief, *Dr. Seuss Enterprises*.

¹⁷⁷ *Dr. Seuss Enterprises, L.P.*, 109 F.3d 1394 at 1401.

¹⁷⁸ Note, I do not comment on the desirability of the holding in this case and there exists criticism of the analytical approach taken by the court. See e.g. Gregory K. Jung, *Dr. Seuss Enterprises v. Penguin Books*, 13 Berkeley Tech. L.J. 119 (1998), Gallagher note, *On the Fair Use Fence*, *supra* note 138 at 766.

¹⁷⁹ *Suntrust Bank v. Houghton Mifflin Co.*, 268 F.3d 1257 (11th Cir. 2001).

¹⁸⁰ *Id.* at 1267.

¹⁸¹ DAVID S. ROH, *ILLEGAL LITERATURE: TOWARD A DISRUPTIVE CREATIVITY* 51 (2015) (Chapter 1, Dead Authors, Copyright Laws, and Parodic Fictions).

¹⁸² *Suntrust Bank*, 268 F.3d at 1270.

balancing that would likely occur in other jurisdictions, even if there is agreement that such forms of parody should be protected.¹⁸³

Ultimately, copyright infringement suits present a powerful opportunity to enforce the moral rights of attribution and integrity for fiction. While fair use has the potential to curb this enforcement, the situations where it is implicated in an undesirable manner are rare. Fanfiction implicates the right of integrity but is practically less relevant due to the nature of copyright suits. Parody implicates the right of integrity, yet is generally protected even in countries with moral rights. Yet there is a slice of situations (likely only faced by sophisticated and well-known authors) where the harm to integrity is so egregious as to override the protections to parody. And those are the only circumstances in which incidental protections fail to effectuate moral rights. On the other hand, academic authors face the idea-expression distinction that limits copyright protection for their works. The strength of copyright infringement as an enforcement mechanism is thus industry dependent.

3. Digital Works: Additional Infringement and Protections

The internet is a large source of copyright infringement, and attempts to protect copyright in the online sphere similarly brings incidental protection to moral rights. After all, the DMCA's safe harbor system¹⁸⁴ has the practical implication of incentivizing content removal by platforms, both at low cost for the potential plaintiff, and without consideration of fair use.¹⁸⁵ Platforms often have their own copyright strike systems based on top of the safe harbor, further facilitating reporting. The non-consideration of fair use may chill the creation of followup works, and there have been additional concerns on the hijacking of copyright strike systems by bad faith actors.¹⁸⁶ Yet for the purposes of a moral rights by contract

¹⁸³ Note that Keller, *Derivative Works Right As a A Moral Right*, *supra* note 138 at 549, cites the argument that property rights on derivative works cannot be justified under utilitarian grounds as support for her suggestion of reforming the derivative works right into a compulsory license – with a limited right of integrity carve-out (supported by non-utilitarian grounds). To the extent that her derivative works argument is true, it may suggest simultaneously excessive and insufficient incidental protections under copyright.

¹⁸⁴ 17 U.S.C. § 512.

¹⁸⁵ Jennifer M. Urban, Joe Karaganis, & Brianna L. Schofield, Notice and Takedown in Everyday Practice, The Takedown Project (2016) (conducting studies that demonstrate fair use concerns in takedown requests).

¹⁸⁶ See e.g. Mike Masnick, How A Feud Among Wolf-Kink Erotica FanFic Authors Demonstrates What The Copyright Office Got Wrong In Its DMCA Report, *techdirt*, May 26, 2020,

regime, such practices that allow for enforcement at low cost generally enhances the level of moral rights protection in the non-contractual context. This mitigates the issues of infringement over the internet.

Not only have trade book publishers launched takedown notices against ebook piracy,¹⁸⁷ but fanfiction has been a target of takedown notices as well.¹⁸⁸ The fact that a fanfiction site had stopped hosting Anne Rice fan fiction due to her threats of legal action¹⁸⁹ reflects the potential effectiveness of sustained legal action (even against content that is likely considered fair use). On the other hand, the effectiveness of DMCA's takedown notices against piracy proper are simultaneously limited, as shown by persistent piracy in the scholarly publishing sphere. After all, Sci-Hub has the ability to regularly switch domain names.¹⁹⁰

A potential additional source of protection for digital works lies in the DMCA's anti-circumvention rules. At the first instance, a work that is perfectly technologically protected would only be subject to contractual relations, thus enabling a moral rights by contracts regime. The DMCA's anti-circumvention provisions supplements the imperfection of existing technological measures by penalizing the "circumvention of access controls", as well as trafficking in

<https://www.techdirt.com/articles/20200525/23544244573/how-feud-among-wolf-kink-erotica-fanfic-authors-demonstrates-what-copyright-office-got-wrong-dmca-report.shtml> (two erotica authors sending take down notices against one another for common genre elements likely considered scenes a faire). See generally, Takedown Hall of Shame, Electronic Frontier Foundation, <https://www.eff.org/takedowns/>

¹⁸⁷ Mike Masnick, Totally Bogus DMCA Takedowns From Giant Publishers Completely Nuke Book Review Blog Off The Internet, techdirt, January 20, 2022, [techdirt.com/articles/20220119/22530648321/totally-bogus-dmca-takedowns-giant-publishers-completely-nuke-book-review-blog-off-internet.shtml](https://www.techdirt.com/articles/20220119/22530648321/totally-bogus-dmca-takedowns-giant-publishers-completely-nuke-book-review-blog-off-internet.shtml) (trade book publishers hiring third party that sent takedown notices to book reviews),

¹⁸⁸ See e.g. Deleted User, DMCA request for fanfiction - US based website, server in Oregon, Reddit, December 03, 2013, https://www.reddit.com/r/legaladvice/comments/1s1by0/dmca_request_for_fanfiction_us_based_website/ (receiving a take down notice from Pottermore, J.K Rowling's Harry Potter website), Sam-maximum, fanfictions come under dmca?, LowEndTalk, April 2013, <https://lowendtalk.com/discussion/9514/fanfictions-come-under-dmca> (receiving a few reports under DMCA), E. Zachary Knight, Where Fan Fiction Stands On Copyright: A Legal Primer, techdirt, August 16, 2012, <https://www.techdirt.com/articles/20120814/20110220055/where-fan-fiction-stands-copyright-legal-primer.shtml> (mentioning the "over zealous use of the DMCA, cease and desist letters and other takedown notices that companies use.")

¹⁸⁹ Where has Anne Rice fanfiction gone?, Fanlore, https://fanlore.org/wiki/Where_has_Anne_Rice_fanfiction_gone%3F (site also claims that there was harassment involved).

¹⁹⁰ Daniel S Himmelstein et al., *Sci-Hub provides access to nearly all scholarly literature*, 7 eLife (2018).

technology that enables the circumvention.¹⁹¹ Anti-circumvention provisions are implicated by the use of DRM in ebooks,¹⁹² as well as paywalled content in scholarly publishing.¹⁹³

Given rampant copyright infringement online,¹⁹⁴ there is likely little practical difference in the level of protection brought on by access controls. After all, there is no substantial procedural benefit to Section 1201 – unlike the DMCA safe harbor provisions which encourages physical removal. Nevertheless, as a theoretical matter, an interpretation of anti-circumvention rules that does not provide for a fair use exception may increase the incidental protection of moral rights.

There is no explicit fair use exception to circumvention rules in the DMCA, and interpretations have been controversial with scholars and civil society supporting a fair use exception and industry being against it.¹⁹⁵ While some courts have held that the fair use defense does not apply to circumvention rules,¹⁹⁶ other courts have suggested that fair use remains applicable.¹⁹⁷ To the extent that the fair use defense is unavailable in such cases, the anti-circumvention provisions theoretically provide enhanced coverage to works with technological protection measures. This would cover the zone that fair use otherwise carves out, a small slice of parodies in publishing but potentially greater in other subjects of copyright such as photography. Yet the potential chilling effect on fair use¹⁹⁸ may mean enhanced

¹⁹¹ 17 U.S.C. § 1201

¹⁹² Ana Carolina Bittar, *Unlocking the Gates of Alexandria: DRM, Competition and Access to E-Books* (2015) (available on SSRN https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2620354)

¹⁹³ Cf. Theresa M. Troupson, note, *Yes, It's Illegal to Cheat A Paywall: Access Rights and the Dmca's Anticircumvention Provision*, 90 N.Y.U.L. Rev. 325, 327 (2015) (using the example of paywalls for news articles).

¹⁹⁴ E.g. Online copyright infringement tracker survey (10th Wave) executive summary, UK Intellectual Property Office, Mar 30, 2021, <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/online-copyright-infringement-tracker-survey-10th-wave/online-copyright-infringement-tracker-survey-10th-wave-executive-summary> (citing the overall online percentage media consumption that is infringing at 23%).

¹⁹⁵ See e.g. David Nimmer, *A Riff on Fair Use in the Digital Millennium Copyright Act*, 148 U. Pa. L. Rev. 673 (2000). Jeff Sharp, *Coming Soon to Pay-Per-View: How the Digital Millennium Copyright Act Enables Digital Content Owners to Circumvent Educational Fair Use*, 40 Am. Bus. L.J. 1, 40 (2002), Digital Millennium Copyright Act, Electronic Frontier Foundation, <https://www.eff.org/issues/dmca>

¹⁹⁶ See e.g., *Universal City Studios, Inc. v. Reimerdes*, 111 F.Supp.2d 294, 304 (S.D.N.Y.,2000)

¹⁹⁷ See, e.g. *Chamberlain Grp., Inc. v. Skylink Techs., Inc.*, 381 F.3d 1178, 1202 (Fed. Cir. 2004).

¹⁹⁸ See e.g. Sharp, *Coming soon to Pay-Per-view*, *supra* note 195 at 15 (describing “the unwillingness of academic institutions to litigate from a defensive posture.”), Digital Millennium Copyright Act, Electronic Frontier Foundation, <https://www.eff.org/issues/dmca> (“Yet the [anti-

theoretical moral rights protection even where a finding of copyright infringement is required.

To the extent that such rules benefit anyone in practice, they would primarily benefit authors contracting with trade / academic publishers who have the resources to protect the works with technological protection measures. Yet given the availability of ebook publishing platforms such as Apple and Amazon, interested self-publishing authors may also take advantage of DRM.¹⁹⁹

Finally, for the right of attribution specifically, the Copyright Office's moral rights report has extensively discussed 17 U.S.C. § 1202: the DMCA's prohibitions against the intentional removal of "copyright management information" (CMI).²⁰⁰ While there was some controversy in the interpretation of this provision,²⁰¹ courts have recently moved away from the traditional narrow interpretation that limits CMIs to "technological measures",²⁰² to a broader one that encompasses conventional identifications of the author or work title (including at the corners of photos).²⁰³ While a narrower interpretation would have had similar implications to the anti-circumvention provisions above – that is little practical effect – the broader interpretation has the potential to bring greater attribution protections, including in the analog space.²⁰⁴

The Copyright Office notes two challenges with Section 1202, the lack of an affirmative right to be credited, as well as difficulties in proving the knowledge requirement for a CMI violation.²⁰⁵ Though both academic and trade publishing

circumvention provisions of the] DMCA has become a serious threat that jeopardizes fair use, impedes competition and innovation, and chills free expression and scientific research.”).

¹⁹⁹ E.g. Is it possible to self-publish ebooks with DRM?, StackExchange, December 23, 2013, <https://ebooks.stackexchange.com/questions/312/is-it-possible-to-self-publish-ebooks-with-drm>, Should I enable DRM on my eBook?, Quora, <https://www.quora.com/Should-I-enable-DRM-on-my-eBook>

²⁰⁰ U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 83 - 100.

²⁰¹ E.g. *Id.* at 87 (“[W]hile the applicability of the provision to analog as well as digital works was initially questioned, such applicability is now well-settled.”), Russell W. Jacobs, *Gutters and Hyperlinks: The Dmca and Proper Position of Copyright Management Information*, 11 Nw. J. Tech. & Intell. Prop. 163, 164 (2013).

²⁰² See U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 88 (discussing cases such as *IQ Grp., Ltd. v. Wiesner Pub., LLC*, 409 F. Supp. 2d 587 (D.N.J. 2006)).

²⁰³ See *id.* at 89 - 90 (discussing cases such as *Murphy v. Millennium Radio Grp. LLC*, 650 F.3d. 295, 299 (3d Cir. 2011))

²⁰⁴ See Kyle Dickinson, note, *Copyright Management Murk: Murphy v. Millennium Radio Group and the Encroachment of the Digital Millennium Copyright Act into the Analog Realm*, 22 DePaul J. Art, Tech. & Intell. Prop. L. 485, 514 (2012)

²⁰⁵ U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 90, 93.

generally have attribution as the default on the original works, the knowledge requirement is more problematic. Even with verbatim copying of passages, it may be difficult to demonstrate that CMI removal was done with “the knowledge that the removal or alteration will induce, enable, facilitate, or conceal copyright infringement.”²⁰⁶ Such a requirement goes far beyond the strict liability analysis applied in copyright infringement cases and ultimately limits the applicability of the CMI provisions.

4. Financial and agency problems in enforcement

The above analysis assumes that claims will actually be filed with the objective of protecting the author’s moral rights interest. Yet copyright lawsuits are widely known to be expensive, lengthy, and not for the faint of heart.²⁰⁷ A statutory moral rights regime thus has the potential to be superior even for areas that are currently incidentally protected, if the regime generates lawsuits that are procedurally simpler or otherwise more favoring of plaintiffs.²⁰⁸

Additionally, given the expense of lawsuits, an agency problem may arise where the actual author does not have the right to sue, including situations where they have assigned their copyright for a flat fee, or where work-for-hire doctrine applies.²⁰⁹ After all, while owner-author interests are aligned in many copyright infringement situations,²¹⁰ they are not aligned in all of them. This is particularly problematic for academic publishing as well as other non-trade book publishing.

Suppose a scholar publishes in a subscription-based academic journal with one publisher.²¹¹ This generally involves assigning copyright to the publisher for

²⁰⁶ Id. at 93. But see Dickinson, *Copyright Management Murk*, *supra* note 204 at 513-14 (suggesting significant impact on settlement even with the mental state issue).

²⁰⁷ The fact that breach of contract suits may be cheaper enhances the level of protection in the contractual space relative to the non-contractual space. A countervailing factor that raises the protections in the non-contractual space however involves the availability of statutory damages, at least to resourced sophisticated parties who registered their works (other factors include the alternative of defendant’s profits, the greater availability of attorney’s fees etc).

²⁰⁸ Protection would also be superior if damages were generally greater as compared to copyright claims or injunctions were easier to obtain (cf. VARA’s prohibitions on destruction for works of recognized stature. 17 U.S.C. § 106A(a)(3)(B)).

²⁰⁹ The authors are not beneficial owners of the copyright in such circumstances and as such are unable to sue. § 5:152. Beneficial ownership, 2 Patry on Copyright § 5:152.

²¹⁰ E.g. publishers wanting to eliminate unauthorized copies (that did not attribute) incidentally supporting the writer’s need for attribution.

²¹¹ Example modified from Anonymous academic, *Plagiarism is rife in academia*, *supra* note 130.

free.²¹² Then another scholar copies parts of the first author's text and publishes another article in a different journal owned by a different publisher. Depending on whether norms are sufficient to sanction the plagiariser, the first author may desire to sue for copyright infringement due to a suffering of psychic harm from the misattribution. Yet this author is unable to sue given their lack of ongoing material financial interest. And the first publisher will also have little incentive to sue due to their bulk journal subscription business model.²¹³ Due to industry norms, a scholar cannot plausibly negotiate with the publisher to have them start a lawsuit, even if this scholar is both sophisticated and well-resourced.²¹⁴

The specifics of this hypothetical raises questions on whether a lawsuit would be efficient in this context (unclear as the firm may suffer reputational and financial harm with lawsuits). And the more general question is whether a contract would address this issue. While contracts are unlikely to address it in the academic context, it is possible that one can negotiate a contract in another field such as with employment or work-for-hire agreements. Even so, the cost of negotiations suggests that only well-resourced sophisticated parties may obtain employment clauses that enable the use of copyright to enforce moral rights (where it is efficient to do so). A separate statutory moral rights regime has the potential to reach a different result.

The Israeli photography case, *Tsarfati v. Tartakover*,²¹⁵ hints at the resolution to this agency problem. The photographer Tsafati had taken a picture of Egyptian president Anwar Sadat “during his military service as a photographer for an Israel Defense Forces [(“IDF”)] magazine.”²¹⁶ The defendant obtained permission to use the photo in his posters from the Government Press Office who

²¹² See e.g., Wiley publishing agreement.

²¹³ Instead, the large academic publishers mostly sue mass article pirates. See e.g. Elsevier Inc. v. www.Sci-Hub.org, No. 15 CIV. 4282 RWS, 2015 WL 6657363 (S.D.N.Y. Oct. 30, 2015) (suing sci-hub and library genesis). Prof. Kwall, *Caught in the Crossfire*, *supra* note 145 at 998 - 99 describes a similar issue in the music industry with the record company licensing a performance they were assigned the copyright of, and then the defendants sampling without attribution.

²¹⁴ Note, forms of open access publishing actually remove the agency problem by granting only non-exclusive licenses to the publisher. See e.g. Elsevier open access sample agreement (CC-BY).

²¹⁵ CC (Jer) 19114-08-13 Michael Tsarfati v. David Tratkover (July 20, 2015)

²¹⁶ Ruth Levush, Israel: Photographer's Moral Right over a State-Copyrighted Photograph Recognized, Library of Congress, August 10, 2015, <https://www.loc.gov/item/global-legal-monitor/2015-08-10/israel-photographers-moral-right-over-a-state-copyrighted-photograph-recognized/>

owned the copyright, but did not attribute the photo to Tsarfati.²¹⁷ The court held that moral rights are separate from copyright, personal, and cannot be transferred, thus requiring Tartakover to pay compensation for the attribution violation.²¹⁸ The government's indifference to the enforcement of the military photographer's moral rights showcases the potential for agency costs, and the need for an independent statutory moral rights regime that can resolve such issues.²¹⁹

Yet this agency problem may only appear in a limited number of circumstances. Notably, this situation applies less often in trade-book publishing, as the author often remains a beneficial owner (who can sue) due to their likely receipt of ongoing royalties with publishing agreements. Authors also generally retain their exclusive rights to preparing derivative works. Furthermore, where copying is verbatim, the trade publisher likely has a stronger incentive to act, at least for authors with large sales. However, it is a significant disadvantage of contracts-based moral rights when it does occur, as in academia.

The two parts above have examined the various factors contributing to the functioning of a moral rights regime by contract, including the role of norms, industry structure, and legal doctrine. The next part evaluates the overall effectiveness of such a system for the two publishing industries then draws broader insights on the need for statutory moral rights.

VI. IMPLICATIONS

A. The Effectiveness of contractual Moral Rights in academic and trade publishing

Contractual moral rights function imperfectly in both publishing industries. However, protection is superior for influential authors with clout, and more generally superior in trade publishing due to the greater degree of copyright

²¹⁷ Id.

²¹⁸ Id. This holding is similar to *Shlomo Arad vs Miskal, Channel 10 et al.*, where the military photographer was protected against misattribution to another person. Rakefet Peled, *Are Moral Rights Denied from Servicemen?*, Lexology, December 3, 2017, <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=29f05b9c-3399-4007-bf35-fb5e2359793b>

²¹⁹ Note however that the current Israeli approach is not necessarily effective as Israeli case law on moral rights for military members is mixed and *Tzarfati v. Tartakover* is in conflict with the more recent *Ron Ilan v. Miskal Publishing House* (2017). The court in *Ron Ilan* held that non-attribution to the military photographer was acceptable as the IDF spokesperson requested no individual credit, that service members have no expectation to receive individual credit, and policy concerns of unit cohesion. Id.

protection in the field. After all, influential authors are more likely to be professionally represented and thus less vulnerable to heuristics. Norms also function more effectively for such authors. And they have the greatest likelihood of negotiating deviations from problematic industry standards (or norms).

On the contractual prong, explicit attribution clauses are not standard. And there have been unsophisticated trade book authors who signed contracts granting the publisher the rights to unilaterally make edits, a result of either their lack of knowledge or heuristics such as overoptimism.²²⁰ On the other hand, if a well-known trade-book author with professional representation insists on an explicit attribution clause, they will receive one. Yet this well-known author's status also suggests that the clause is less necessary, given the publisher incentives to attribute (for marketing) and to maintain the relationship — a product of the trade publishing business model.

It is more difficult to obtain such clauses as a less well-resourced or unsophisticated author. And the practical alternative of open licensing requires at least some degree of sophistication in choosing the license (let alone writing one). Resources are also necessary for open licensing, as an author needs to survive financially with their work licensed in such a manner. With this alternative more easily achieved in academic publishing, or by those with other sources of income, authors instead rely on norms that supplement the contract on the fronts of attribution and integrity.

Yet norms deviate on the contractual front. While attribution norms by the publisher are generally powerful, the norms of academic co-authorship (contracts uncommon, perhaps as a result of unsophistication or overoptimism) allow for the entering of power-dynamics that disadvantage students and junior faculty. The broader industry structure of academia thus plays a role in impeding moral rights.

The situation is similar on the non-contractual front, as wealthier trade book authors have the opportunity to enforce their moral rights through copyright infringement suits. For such authors, copyright grants a large amount of incidental protection, with the only gap being the fair use status of egregious parodies.²²¹ This is not the case for academic authors, who suffer the agency problem of being unable to sue, and the expression-idea distinction even when they have the standing to sue.

²²⁰ See Strauss, *Editing Clauses in Publishing Contracts*, *supra* note 40.

²²¹ Non-commercial fan fiction, while also likely fair use, can be deterred through the threat of lawsuits and DMCA. This situation may be socially undesirable given the widespread enjoyment of fan fiction for their creators.

Again, while non-contract-space norms of attribution (against plagiarism) exist in academia, they are effective more so for senior academics. Early-career researchers instead have particular difficulty against senior academics' plagiarism. The requirement for sophistication and the poor performance of non-senior academics showcases the limitations of a contracts-based moral rights system in effectuating moral rights.

Of course, limitations in moral rights effectuation only affect the creative incentives of the sophisticated subset of the creators. On the academic front, it is unclear whether entering graduate students recognize the potential for negative experiences associated with graduate schools.²²² Students may have further held beliefs that university officials would resolve such plagiarism problems.²²³ Yet such students ultimately learn of the actual situation when they become the victims of plagiarism²²⁴ or hear of others' experiences. After all, 5% of respondents in a survey of psychology doctoral graduates "agreed that their mentor took credit for their work."²²⁵ And by the time one reaches academic chemistry faculty, 50% reported "not receiving appropriate credit for contributions they had made . . . , including when they themselves were students."²²⁶ Junior faculty's incentives may then be suboptimal, though "publish or perish" likely already generates sufficient (even excessive) incentives to create. Note that norms against plagiarism are more effective when invoked by senior faculty, increasing the relative effectiveness of the system for them.

There are parallels with trade book publishing, as it is unclear whether a significant number of early-career authors recognize the issues.²²⁷ On the other

²²² Becker, *Graduate students' experiences*, *supra* note 29 at 253 ("[S]tudents expect a positive experience in Higher Education despite the power differentials with faculty that exist.") (internal citations removed).

²²³ E.g. *id* at 259. ("Mike lost faith in university officials to care about integrity") (suggesting that students may have had faith in the first place).

²²⁴ For at least some, this process may come with damaging increases of cynicism and trauma that society may want to minimize. See e.g. Becker, *Graduate students' experiences*, *supra* note 29 at 261-62 (contrasting one of the graduate student interviewee's feelings of abuse and trauma, changing in her ability to trust others, after experiencing retaliation by the university who threatened to retract her PhD, with another interviewee who "continues to have 'very fond memories' of his doctoral programme.").

²²⁵ Richard A. Clark, Sherry L. Harden, & W. Brad Johnson, *Mentor relationships in clinical psychology doctoral training: Results of a national survey*, 27(4) *Teaching of Psychology* 262, 265 (2000).

²²⁶ Seeman & House, *U.S. Academic Chemical Community*, *supra* note 97 at 346.

²²⁷ See their willingness to sign clauses enabling unilateral publisher edits.

hand, established, well-resourced, authors can and do effectuate moral rights in both contract and infringement suits. Discounting the thin slice that is egregious parodies,²²⁸ it is only those sophisticated yet less well-resourced authors who may ultimately be negatively incentivized by the limits of a contractual moral rights system.²²⁹ Though to the extent that moral rights suits are as equally expensive as copyright suits, the degree of deterrence and consequently creative incentives may be nearly identical in the two systems.

A contracts-based system's effects on incentives may thus only be negative for a limited subset of the creator population. At the same time, ex-post psychic harms from inefficient moral rights effectuation is a social harm. The limitations of contract-based moral rights in both forms of publishing are thus clear.

B. Supporting Statutory Rights Regimes

Thus a statutory system of moral rights can be attractive. The primary benefit of such a system is its ability to efficiently generate moral rights in situations where contracts and incidental protection fall short. This includes failures in contracting such as the lack of explicit attribution clauses in trade book publishing. The system also covers areas where copyright doctrine (idea-expression distinction, joint authorship, fair use) and industry standards (agency problems with academic authors) would otherwise limit the enforceability through incidental protection. Furthermore, a statutory rights system allows for narrow tailoring – the ability to protect only moral rights where it is efficient to do so – instead of the all-or-nothing of enforcing both moral and economic rights with protection through copyright.²³⁰

However, there is a tradeoff on the contractual space between (1) a system with waivers, which recognizes the possibility that enforcing a given moral right may be inefficient, and (2) a non-waivable system, which will effectuate moral rights for non-sophisticated, less well-resourced actors, even against industry standards.

²²⁸ Given their unlikelihood, sophisticated yet boundedly rational authors are more likely to treat the possibility as “zero” than significant, except in the aftermath of a parody violation due to the availability heuristic.

²²⁹ See E.g. Concepción de León, *Nora Roberts Sues Brazilian Writer Who She Says Plagiarized Her Work*, *New York Times*, April 24, 2019, <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/04/24/books/nora-roberts-plagiarism.html> (quoting her as stating that “A lot of the other writers involved in this, they don’t have the money to fight it. I do have the money.”).

²³⁰ Philpot’s copyleft trolling would be less of an issue if the remedy to good faith non-attribution under a moral rights statute is mandatory attribution and a public notice.

After all, the problems of bargaining power inequality and unsophisticated parties suggest the possibility that waivers will be over-adopted, reducing the utility gain from a waivable statutory system.²³¹ The fact that even sophisticated players may lack the resources to negotiate a movement away from the industry standard further strikes against a system with waivers. Yet some gains in the contractual space remain as well-resourced sophisticated parties who do not waive obtain the benefits of the increased protection, as with professionally represented artists under VARA. Furthermore, where neither party is sophisticated, as in the academic co-authorship context, the default rule remains powerful. Also, such a concern likely only implicates the efficient moral rights effectuation issue rather than the incentives for creation issue, as unsophisticated parties are less affected, *ex-ante*, due to their overly optimistic expectations. Finally, there is always the possibility that courts sanction waivers, *ex-post*, in the most egregious of circumstances. All of the above mitigates the issues associated with a waiver system. And if the concerns of inefficient over-enforcement prevail, then a waiver system is beneficial.

The contractual space benefits of either statutory system are potentially reduced by issues associated with the endowment or creativity effect. Sprigman et al. have suggested the problem of reduced trade associated with the increased valuation of moral rights in a system where moral rights are the default rule.²³² Yet given the arbitrary nature of the initial financial valuations in that study, it is unclear whether the reduction in trade is undesirable. In fact, it may very well be that the psychic harms associated with non-attribution are undervalued by the author due to their optimism. After all, ghostwriters have described increasing psychological tolls and disadvantages that they did not expect when they entered the field.²³³ Valuations are inevitably difficult when it comes to psychic harms.

Moving on to the non-contractual space, both a mandatory system and a waiver system have the potential to bring significant benefits in enhancing moral rights protections. Here, the tradeoff between the two is less salient. After all, waivers

²³¹Cotter, *Pragmatism*, *supra* note 4 at 87 (“the advantages of a waivable right may be quite limited if . . . , artists who are asked to waive their rights often will have little choice but to agree to do so.”). Cotter compares, in the VARA context, waivable moral rights, mandatory moral rights, and no moral rights. *Id.* at 2.

²³² Sprigman et al., *What is a name worth?*, *supra* note 4 at 1420 (specifically talking about attribution). Cotter, *Pragmatism*, *supra* note 4 at 61 (suggesting endowment effect concerns for integrity right).

²³³ See *supra* note 28.

such as those required by VARA can be use-specific.²³⁴ And while a firm in a contractual relationship may desire a waiver for its use of the work, there is a reduced incentive to demand a waiver for all other situations and all other users as well. Sample waivers for VARA available online currently showcases both the type that waives moral rights for all situations and users, as well as the type that only waives for the contract parties.²³⁵ If the type of waiver that only waives for the contract parties becomes popularized under a waiver system, then the system will generate results closer to a mandatory regime on the non-contractual space. The primary trade-off between a waiver and a mandatory system then becomes salient only in the situations where the author desires a lawsuit but the publisher does not (bad publicity for example). There, a mandatory system may potentially permit inefficient lawsuits and vice versa with the waiver.

Ultimately, the magnitude of a statutory moral rights system's efficiency benefits depend on the salience of the re-use space that contract and other laws fail to cover. Where such coverage failure is significant, statutory moral rights will bring meaningful benefits. And even a waiver system has the potential to benefit not only sophisticated players contractually but also authors generally in the non-contractual space.

C. Improving contractual moral rights regimes

Yet in principle, it is not strictly necessary to implement a statutory system to obtain the benefits, as one can adjust other laws to increase the contractual moral rights system's zone of coverage.²³⁶ Adjusting fair use is the most salient, though it is not the only doctrine that may be adjusted to better effectuate moral rights.

²³⁴ 17 U.S.C. § 106A(e)(1) (The waiver “shall specifically identify the work, and uses of that work, to which the waiver applies, and the waiver shall apply only to the work and uses so identified.”).

²³⁵ See VARA Waiver Sample Clauses, Law Insider, <https://www.lawinsider.com/clause/vara-waiver> (compare “The artist has waived his or her rights under the Visual Artists Rights Act as described in the attached exhibit “C”.”, to “artist waives any and all claims, arising at any time and under any circumstances, against the City, its officers, agents, employees, successors and assigns under the federal Visual Artists Rights Act”), Westlaw Edge Copyright License Agreement (Pro-Licensor) USA (“Licensor waives . . . ‘Moral Rights’ with respect to the use of the Work pursuant to this Agreement.”).

²³⁶ The Copyright Office has suggested improvements to the “patchwork” including changes to the Lanham Act (to include “false representations regarding authorship”), VARA (to add clarifying definitions, guidance, etc), and Section 1202 (to improve CMI protections when removal is “intended to conceal attribution.”). U.S. Copyright Office, *Authors, Attribution, and Integrity*, *supra* note 6 at 39-40.

On the non-contractual front, adjusting fair use analysis to incorporate attribution as a factor (similar to Israel’s locally criticized practice), will improve the incidental protection provided by copyright for the right of attribution.²³⁷ This change is not likely to make a substantial impact for trade publishing given the broad coverage of copyright infringement for the subject matter, though it will likely benefit fields such as photography where dynamics differ. On the other hand, it is also unlikely to be a significant shift practically given the fact that attribution is already occasionally considered as a part of the implicit good or bad faith analysis that courts at times have done (even if this good / bad analysis is criticized).²³⁸ The right of integrity, however, may require broader changes to fair use analysis given the apparent conflict between the two.²³⁹ Even so, penalizing cases of egregious work distortion in fair use analysis may also provide for improved performance — coverage of a small slice of parodies for publishing, yet potentially significant in other fields.

Other changes that may have the incidental benefits of improving contractual moral rights include procedural shifts in copyright that favor plaintiffs or alternatively streamlining the process, given the issues associated with copyright litigation. Moral rights may also be improved upon by a shift in the default rules surrounding joint works into the more European mutual agreement to exploit model. Though this avoids the issue of non-attribution and non-integrity against past and present co-authors in situations without contracts (most co-authored scholarly papers), transactions costs may be increased. If so, a narrowly tailored statutory moral rights rule may be superior. This situation of potentially substantial transaction costs is similar in the case of loosening the definition of beneficial

²³⁷ This argument supports the myriad of other reasons provided for adding attribution as a factor, including, e.g. Greg Lastowka, *Digital Attribution: Copyright and the Right to Credit*, 87 B.U. L. Rev. 41, 84 (2007), Cameron, *Reinvigorating U.S. Copyright with Attribution*, *supra* note 32 at 151.

²³⁸ See Stanford Libraries, *Measuring Fair Use: The Four Factors*, Stanford Libraries, <https://fairuse.stanford.edu/overview/fair-use/four-factors/> (“The “Fifth” Fair Use Factor: Are You Good or Bad?”). Cameron, *Reinvigorating U.S. Copyright with Attribution*, *supra* note 32 at 139-40 (describing the potential that attribution evidences fair use, but also raising situations that “evidence of attribution cut against a fair use”). More generally, courts have used “bad faith” to “encompass a wide range of conduct weighing against a finding of fair use. Simon J. Frankel & Matt Kellogg, *Bad Faith and Fair Use*, 60 J. Copyright Socy. U.S.A. 1, 1 (2012) (ultimately arguing that “courts should drop all considerations of bad faith from fair use.”). Note however given the copyleft troll cases, see *supra* note 125-32 and accompanying text, that bad faith and non-attribution do not always align. Thus an explicit analysis of attribution has the potential to impact results.

²³⁹ See e.g.: Smith, *Creative Destruction*, *supra* note 107 at 602 (for visual art). See also the discussion of parody in *supra* section V.B.2.

ownership to include both actual authors in work-for-hire situations and those who no longer possess financial interests in the work.

On the contractual front, incidental moral rights benefits may provide some support for enabling the contracting out of fair use, as well as more flexibility in contracting generally (including for liquidated damages), though this concern is more theoretical than practical for publishing. Benefits from changes in such doctrines, however, will primarily benefit sophisticated parties with the resources to negotiate contractual terms that shifts away from the industry standards.

Here, a push for boilerplate contractual clauses that explicitly require attribution (or integrity) may be effective at improving contractual outcomes both in rare circumstances, as well as potentially for unsophisticated parties. The fact that norms and expectations have allowed publishing contracts to exist without explicit authorship attribution clauses is problematic in those rare situations without attribution (see *supra* Section IV.A.2). Yet it is exactly in these situations that a clause even as vague as “the author shall be attributed for material written by the author where it is reasonable to do so” will come into effect. Such a clause or similar clauses should be relatively easy to amend into the contract by a sophisticated well-resourced actor given the expectation on both sides that the author be attributed. And on the off chance such a clause does become boilerplate, then it can benefit unsophisticated parties as well, *ex-post*.

Adjusting fair use to accommodate for moral rights may do much to improve protections on the non-contractual front. The side effects associated with adjusting other laws suggests that a statutory system may ultimately more efficiently track the authors’ moral rights needs.

CONCLUSION

This paper attempted to explore the degree to which the moral rights of attribution and integrity may be effectuated through a contracts-based system. While contracts at first appear to have the critical disadvantage of being unable to bind third parties, other causes of action such as copyright infringement have the potential to incidentally protect moral rights. For trade book publishing, problems in contracting serve as the main limitations on the contractual front, with fair use analysis (egregious parodies) being an additional concern on the non-contractual front. On the other hand, academic publishing faces a myriad of problems not only

in contracting, but also copyright doctrine (idea-expression distinction etc), with academia's norms instead inconsistently effectuating moral rights.

Only for sophisticated well-resourced players in fields with good incidental protections from other laws (e.g. low applicability of fair use), will a contracts-based system effectively effectuate moral rights and incentivize creation. The existence of contractual-space norms allows trade book publishing to approach this effective effectuation for well-resourced sophisticated authors, while more powerful academic authors may similarly benefit from academia's non-contract-space norms against plagiarism. Yet even as the contracts-based system fails to optimally effectuate moral rights under other circumstances, incentives to create will remain similar for unsophisticated players due to their optimistic expectations and lack of information. This category includes early-career trade authors as well as graduate students.²⁴⁰ Setting aside the intermediate sophisticated yet poorly resourced authors (including potentially junior faculty) whose incentives to create may be affected, the primary source of inefficiencies is instead ex-post — where psychological harms arise from needless moral rights violations.²⁴¹

The limitations of a contracts-based system suggests that a statutory regime, and to a lesser extent, adjustments to other laws, can bring efficiency gains. While such gains mostly involve reducing ex-post harms, they may also raise the creative incentives of sophisticated authors for whom inefficient effectuation is relevant. Finally, while mandatory and waiver systems do present a trade-off, one should recognize their similar non-contractual space benefits alongside the identical benefits for contract-space relations between non-sophisticated parties.

²⁴⁰ To the extent that there is a moral obligation to debias authors on their misconceptions (as I believe there to be), doing so will incidentally decrease their incentives to create (or perhaps enter the field of academia). Under such circumstances, more systematic change, either within institutions or with a mandatory statutory moral rights system will generate superior results.

²⁴¹ To the extent that moral rights are justified solely under reputational externalities, this issue may be irrelevant. If so, any improvements in moral rights effectuation under a statutory regime should be evaluated under solely an efficient reputation generation (and protection) criteria. Sprigman et. al.'s concerns of the endowment effect's reduction on trades similarly become more powerful (due to the irrelevance of the psychic harms valuation problem). The implications of both may be a reduction in the optimal level of moral rights. Note that potential improvements to the ex-ante creative incentives of sophisticated players (from a consideration of psychic harms) remain important even if the efficient effectuation criteria is altered.